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Solving the Nonlinear Vlasov Equation on a Quantum Computer

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Abstract

Quantum computers are naturally suited to solving linear problems, however most scientifically and technologically relevant physical systems are governed by nonlinear differential equations. In this report we investigate solving a nonlinear plasma model, the Vlasov equation, using a state of the art quantum algorithm. We show that the Vlasov equation, discretized on a $(1+1)$ dimensional grid and coupled to Krook type collision operators, can be mapped entirely onto the framework of a recent quantum algorithm developed for systems of ordinary differential equations with quadratic nonlinearities. We generalize the framework to an arbitrary number of plasma species. We demonstrate that for certain sets of plasma parameters the quantum algorithm is guaranteed to converge to the correct solution. Lastly, we use these results to derive the asymptotic scaling of the gate complexity of the quantum algorithm in the limit of large grid sizes. We conclude that the upper bound for the gate complexity is polynomially larger than the time complexity of the best classical algorithms.

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I declare that the contents of Appendix [B](#) were derived with my project partner and that those of Chapters [2-4](#) summarize results from literature. Everything else in this report is my original work.

Layperson’s Summary:
Solving Nonlinear Plasma Problems on Quantum Computers

First of all, what is plasma and what is a quantum computer? Well, plasma can be imagined as a mixture of different gases that are each electrically charged. It is essentially a phase of matter that has numerous scientific and technological applications, most importantly inertial confinement fusion. However, simulating its behaviour is very computationally expensive and often proves to be intractable even with modern day supercomputers. This is where quantum computers come into the picture. It has been realized that the computational power of future quantum computers will be far superior to that of classical devices for certain problems. The famous example is their ability to break the RSA encryption. We also hope they can be used for solving scientific problems, such as performing plasma simulations efficiently. Now, this is where the catch is, quantum computers are only naturally suited to solving so-called linear problems, while plasma physics ones are generally nonlinear. Linearity means that the size of the effects are proportional to the actions causing them, just as acceleration is proportional to the force causing it in Newton’s law. As a result of this restriction, the plasma models that have been solved with quantum algorithms, i.e. algorithms that can be run on quantum computers, only describe the linear regime of plasma. Note that by ‘solving a model’, we mean the numerical computation of the state of the system at some later time, from initial conditions. However, the mentioned linear regime is only approximate since nonlinearity is at the heart of most physically relevant plasma phenomena, such as turbulence and wave-particle interactions, and cannot be neglected in plasma models.

Up until now, no tangible solution was put forward for the quantum simulation of nonlinear plasma models. Our project had the objective of carrying that out for the first time. First, we chose the so-called Vlasov equation as our plasma model to be solved. It describes the time evolution of plasma in terms of distribution functions, that specify how much of the plasma is at a particular position with a particular velocity. These functions slowly thermalize and become static as a result of collisions between particles. Then, we chose a suitable quantum algorithm that can handle quadratic nonlinearities like those in the Vlasov equation. The key part of our project was mapping the Vlasov equation onto the completely different formalism of the quantum algorithm, which encodes the dynamics in matrices. In order to do that, we placed the distribution functions on a discrete grid, i.e. approximated them with series of discrete function values. Next, we derived expressions for the matrices, while keeping the number of grid points as a free variable. This was first done for only one species of dynamically moving particles in the plasma, electrons, and then extended to an arbitrary number of them. The resulting matrices are highly structured and contain appealing patterns. The quantum algorithm used requires these matrices to satisfy strict constraints. Tackling this required bounding many expressions as tightly as possible. Focusing on one species, we found that the constraints are only satisfied if collisions are taken to be very strong, much stronger than they are typically in real life. A potential quantum advantage was also investigated, using the so-called gate complexity of the quantum algorithm. That quantifies runtime and can be compared to the classical equivalent, time complexity. Unfortunately we found that the quantum algorithm is actually slower than the classical one for our case.

To summarize, although not necessarily with physically relevant parameters or with a quantum advantage, but we showed for the first time how the nonlinear Vlasov equation can be solved on a future quantum computer. This work could serve as the basis of future research as there are multiple open questions left. Also, new quantum algorithms with the same matrix formalism as the one used here are actively being developed. It is likely that faster ones will eventually show a quantum advantage and then our mapping can be applied to those.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Organization	2
2	Mathematical preliminaries	3
2.1	Notation table	3
2.2	Norms	4
2.3	Vectorization	4
2.4	Kronecker product	5
2.5	Direct sum	5
2.6	Big \mathcal{O} notation	5
3	The Vlasov equation	7
3.1	Vlasov-Maxwell system	7
3.1.1	Full model	7
3.1.2	(1+1) dimensional model	8
3.2	Collision operator	8
3.3	Discretization scheme	9
3.3.1	Discretizing the coordinates	9
3.3.2	Boundary conditions	10
3.3.3	Discrete calculus	10
3.3.4	Finite difference equation	11
3.4	Physical scenario	12
4	The quantum algorithm	13
4.1	Problem statement	13
4.2	Convergence criteria	13
4.3	The algorithm	14
4.3.1	Input	14
4.3.2	Computational steps	14
4.3.3	Output	15
4.4	Gate complexity	15
5	Mapping for 1 species	16
5.1	Vectorization of the distribution matrix	16
5.1.1	\vec{u}	16
5.1.2	$\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$	17
5.2	Finding the matrices	17
5.2.1	General method	17
5.2.2	$F^{(0)}$	19
5.2.3	$F^{(1)}$	19

5.2.4	$F^{(2)}$	21
6	Convergence and gate complexity for 1 species	23
6.1	Proving convergence	23
6.1.1	Need for a bound	23
6.1.2	Ingredients for the bound	24
6.1.3	Bounding R	30
6.2	Gate complexity	32
6.2.1	Ingredients for the gate complexity	32
6.2.2	Asymptotic scaling of the gate complexity	33
7	Mapping for S species	34
7.1	Vectorization of the distribution matrices	34
7.1.1	\vec{u}	34
7.1.2	$\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$	34
7.2	Finding the matrices	35
7.2.1	$F^{(0)}$	35
7.2.2	$F^{(1)}$	35
7.2.3	$F^{(2)}$	37
7.3	Remarks on convergence and gate complexity	38
8	Summary and prospects	40
A	Expression for the elements of $F^{(2)}$	44
B	Coupling to Ampere's law	46
C	Derivation of bounds for $\ F^{(0)}\$	49

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Plasma physics applications have been in the focus of high-performance scientific computing for the last few decades. The ability to effectively simulate and predict plasma behaviour is key to our understanding of a rich variety of physical phenomena, such as high-energy astrophysics and inertial confinement fusion. However, the capacities of current classical supercomputers often prove to be insufficient for large scale plasma simulations because of the massive time scales and high number of variables involved in these computations. To overcome these limitations many started to seek alternatives to classical computation. One of the candidates is quantum computation, which offers an exponential speedup over certain classical algorithms in terms of computational complexity [1, 2]. The so-called quantum advantage originates from the fact that the number of quantum bits, called qubits, is only logarithmic in the number of classical dynamical variables solved for, as a result of quantum mechanical entanglement between qubits.

Consequently, quantum computing also gained attention in the plasma physics community. Recent reviews [3–5] address the main challenges of mapping plasma problems onto the architecture of quantum computers and discuss the progress made so far. The most notable difficulty that arises in the construction of such mappings is the fact that while plasma models are generally nonlinear, quantum computers can only perform linear and unitary transformations on the state of the qubits. So far this difficulty was mitigated by only concentrating on plasma problems in the linearized regime [6–10]. However, the practicality of this is limited as most plasma phenomena of scientific relevance, such as turbulence, shock waves and wave-particle interactions are strongly nonlinear [11]. The mapping of nonlinear dynamics has been investigated [12–16] but no concrete, tangible solution has been put forward for the quantum simulation of nonlinear plasma models.

The lack of success in solving nonlinear dynamics on a quantum computer was partially due to fact that quantum algorithms for nonlinear differential equations were either inefficient or difficult to apply to actual problems. For example, the first such quantum algorithm had a runtime that scaled exponentially with simulation time [17]. The idea was further improved in [18], bringing down this scaling to quadratic. An alternative approach to the problem was formulated in the form of variational quantum algorithms, that solve nonlinear differential equations as optimization problems in which the computational tasks are divided between a classical and a quantum computer [19–21].

Recently another direction emerged, which is mapping the nonlinear system onto a larger dimensional linear one numerically, as a part of the quantum algorithm. This can be done via techniques such as homotopy perturbation [22] or Carleman linearization [23–26]. These quantum algorithms offer a favourable runtime scaling with respect to simulation time, the

number of dynamical variables and the allowed error on the solution. Another advantage is their simple framework, that, as an input, takes a systems of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) with quadratic nonlinearity, and outputs a quantum state containing information on the solution at later times. This simplicity and scaling comes at the cost of two types of constraints. Firstly, the linear part of the evolution is required to be dissipative, meaning that the norm of the solution vector decreases in time. Note that mathematically, this constraint is implemented differently in the mentioned articles but is qualitatively the same. Secondly, the ratio of the combined strength of nonlinear and inhomogeneous effects to that of linear dissipative ones is required to be small. The exact definition of this constraint also varies between the above articles, but it is typically formulated as $R < 1$ for some so-called convergence parameter R measuring the mentioned ratio.

In this project, the quantum algorithm of Krovi [26] was employed for the purpose of solving the nonlinear Vlasov equation, the cornerstone model of plasma physics, on a future error corrected quantum computer. The procedure developed in this project involves discretizing the Vlasov equation on a finite grid and mapping the dynamics of the resulting finite difference equation onto the framework of [26]. Furthermore, it is shown that the constraints mentioned in the last paragraph can be reliably satisfied for certain regimes of plasma parameters as long as collisions make the system dissipative enough. The mapping is first introduced for one dynamic plasma species and later extended to an arbitrary number of them. As mentioned earlier, nonlinear plasma models have never been solved on quantum computers before, hence the results presented in this report will not only be a proof of principle but also a first step of many on the path of solving general plasma problems on quantum computers.

1.2 Organization

This report is structured as follows. Chapter 2 is dedicated to clarifying the mathematical notation used in the report. Next, Chapter 3 introduces the Vlasov equation and the discretization scheme used to solve this model. Then, in Chapter 4 the quantum algorithm from [26], onto which the Vlasov equation is mapped, is outlined. After that, in Chapter 5 our main results are presented, the mapping from the discretized Vlasov equation with one dynamical species onto the input of [26]. Next, Chapter 6 investigates the convergence parameter R of the quantum algorithm as well as the asymptotic scaling of its runtime with respect to grid size. Then, in Chapter 7 we show how the mapping procedure can be extended to the Vlasov system with an arbitrary number of particle species. Finally, in Chapter 8 we discuss potential extensions of this project and give conclusion on our results.

Appendix A gives an explicit expression for the elements of a matrix discussed in Chapter 5. Then, Appendix B describes an alternative mapping between the Vlasov equation and the quantum algorithm, and concludes why that would not converge. Finally, Appendix C contains derivations of bounds used in Chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Mathematical preliminaries

2.1 Notation table

See Table 2.1 below for the list of notation used in the report. The rest of this chapter discusses norms, vectorization, the Kronecker product, the direct sum and the big \mathcal{O} notation in detail. Note that the $x // y$ notation is not standard, it is used here to treat integer indices with periodicity. It takes x , and subtracts y from it as many times as possible while keeping the result strictly positive.

Symbol	Meaning
v_n	n -th entry of vector \vec{v}
$\ \vec{v}\ $	l_2 norm of vector \vec{v}
A_{ij}	ij -th entry of matrix A
$\ A\ $	spectral norm of matrix A
$\ A\ _F$	Frobenius norm of matrix A
$\mu(A)$	log-norm norm of matrix A
$\text{vec}(A)$	vectorization of matrix A
\mathbb{I}_N	identity matrix of size (N, N)
$0_{N,M}$	zero matrix of size (N, M)
δ_{ij}	Kronecker delta
$\lceil x \rceil$	ceiling of number x
$x // y$	$x - y \left(\left\lceil \frac{x}{y} \right\rceil - 1 \right)$, for integers x, y
$\text{erf}(x)$	$(2/\sqrt{\pi}) \int_0^x \exp(-t^2) dt$
\otimes	Kronecker product
\oplus	direct sum
$\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$	asymptotic scaling

Table 2.1: Summary of the notation used in the report.

2.2 Norms

Norms quantify the magnitude of objects in linear algebra. For vectors the l_2 norm is used:

$$\|\vec{v}\| = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N |v_n|^2}, \quad (2.1)$$

where N is the length of \vec{v} . For matrices the spectral norm is used, which is induced by the above l_2 norm as

$$\|A\| = \max_{\|\vec{x}\| \neq 0} \frac{\|A\vec{x}\|}{\|\vec{x}\|} = \sqrt{\lambda_{\max}(A^\dagger A)}, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\lambda_{\max}(\cdot)$ returns the largest eigenvalue of its input and \dagger denotes Hermitian conjugate. We also use the Frobenius norm for matrices, defined as

$$\|A\|_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M |A_{nm}|^2}, \quad (2.3)$$

for a matrix of size (N, M) . Both matrix norms exist for all matrices. A key identity is that for any matrix A , $\|A\| \leq \|A\|_F$. This will be used later to upper bound $\|A\|$ since the Frobenius norm is easy to calculate analytically, while the spectral norm is not.

The log-norm of an (N, N) square matrix A is given by

$$\mu(A) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\|\mathbb{I}_N + hA\| - 1}{h} = \lambda_{\max}\left(\frac{A + A^T}{2}\right), \quad (2.4)$$

where T is the transpose. Unlike $\|A\|$ and $\|A\|_F$, $\mu(A)$ can take negative values. An important relation is

$$\alpha(A) \leq \mu(A) \leq \|A\|, \quad (2.5)$$

where $\alpha(A) = \max\{\text{Re}(\lambda)\}$ is the largest one of the real parts of the eigenvalues λ of A .

2.3 Vectorization

The vectorization operator takes a matrix and outputs a vector which contains each matrix element once. We choose to work with *row-major* vectorization, that places the elements of the input matrix into the vector row by row going from top to bottom. For an arbitrary matrix A with size (N, M) it acts as

$$\text{vec}(A) = \text{vec} \begin{pmatrix} A_{1,1} & \cdots & A_{1,M} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{N,1} & \cdots & A_{N,M} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{1,1} \\ A_{1,2} \\ \vdots \\ A_{1,M} \\ A_{2,1} \\ \vdots \\ A_{2,M} \\ \vdots \\ A_{N,M} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.6)$$

The resulting $\text{vec}(A)$ has length NM . Note that vectorization is entirely invertible, as long as the size of the target matrix is specified. Vectorization has the property

$$\|\text{vec}(A)\| = \|A\|_F. \quad (2.7)$$

2.4 Kronecker product

The Kronecker product is an operation between matrices, that embeds one into the other. For general matrices A and B with sizes (N, M) and (P, Q) , respectively, it reads

$$A \otimes B = \begin{pmatrix} A_{1,1}B & \cdots & A_{1,M}B \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{N,1}B & \cdots & A_{N,M}B \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.8)$$

where $A_{ij}B$ represents a matrix of size (P, Q) . Then $A \otimes B$ has size (NP, MQ) .

In particular, for column vectors \vec{v} and \vec{u} with lengths N and M , respectively, it reads

$$\vec{v} \otimes \vec{u} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \vec{u} \\ v_2 \vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ v_N \vec{u} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.9)$$

where $v_n \vec{u}$ denotes a vector of length M and $\vec{v} \otimes \vec{u}$ is a vector of length NM .

2.5 Direct sum

In the context of matrix algebra, the direct sum is an operation that takes matrices and places them in a higher dimensional matrix in the form of a block-diagonal chain. For general matrices A and B with sizes (N, M) and (P, Q) , respectively, it reads

$$A \oplus B = \begin{pmatrix} A & 0_{N,Q} \\ 0_{P,M} & B \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.10)$$

where the sizes of the zero matrices are set so that $A \oplus B$ is properly defined and has size $(N + P, M + Q)$.

For multiple matrices $\{A^{(i)}\}$ with $i = 1, \dots, I$, the direct sum can be written compactly as

$$\bigoplus_{i=1}^I A^{(i)} = A^{(1)} \oplus A^{(2)} \oplus \dots \oplus A^{(I)} = \begin{pmatrix} A^{(1)} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & A^{(2)} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & A^{(I)} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.11)$$

The sizes of the zeros can be identified uniquely based on the sizes of the matrices $\{A^{(i)}\}$.

2.6 Big \mathcal{O} notation

The \mathcal{O} notation is used to quantify the asymptotic behaviour of functions. Formally, for real functions $f(x)$, $g(x) > 0$ we say

$$f(x) = \mathcal{O}(g(x)) \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow a \quad (2.12)$$

if there exist positive numbers M , δ such that

$$f(x) \leq Mg(x) \quad \forall x \text{ with } 0 < |x - a| < \delta. \quad (2.13)$$

The following examples explain it better than a definition.

$$\begin{aligned} 4x^2 + x + 10/x &= \mathcal{O}(x^2) && \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty, \\ 2e^x + x^5 + 10 \log(x) &= \mathcal{O}(e^x) && \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty, \\ e^x(2y^2 + y) + y + 2 \log(y)x &= \mathcal{O}(e^x y^2) && \text{as } x, y \rightarrow \infty \quad (2.14) \\ &&& \text{for independent } x \text{ \& } y, \\ x^5 + \log(x) + 2/x^2 &= \mathcal{O}(1/x^2) && \text{as } x \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

Chapter 3

The Vlasov equation

3.1 Vlasov-Maxwell system

3.1.1 Full model

The Vlasov equation describes plasma dynamics within the framework of kinetic theory, in which the state of the system is specified by a set of distribution functions $f^{(s)}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ [11]. Here s labels the particle species, as each species in the plasma has its own $f^{(s)}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t)$. These distribution functions are number densities in the phase space spanned position (\mathbf{r}) and velocity (\mathbf{v}) vectors. Kinetic theory is based on the Boltzmann equation, which in the non-relativistic limit is given by

$$\frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial \mathbf{r}} + \frac{\mathbf{F}_s}{m_s} \cdot \frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = C[f^{(s)}], \quad (3.1)$$

where $\partial/\partial \mathbf{r}$ and $\partial/\partial \mathbf{v}$ are gradients in position and velocity space, respectively. Also, $C[\cdot]$ is a collision operator, m_s is the mass of species s and \mathbf{F}_s is the local force acting on species s . Coupling this equation to Maxwell's equations and setting \mathbf{F}_s equal to the Lorentz force, one obtains the celebrated Vlasov-Maxwell system. It is useful to separate the particle species into dynamic ones and a single fixed one. The dynamic ones carry the label s and have (position spatial) number densities $n_s(\mathbf{r}) = \iiint d^3v f^{(s)}$. The fixed one provides a static background and does not evolve in time. It is labelled with a prime and no letter, i.e. it has (position spatial) number density $n'(\mathbf{r}) = \iiint d^3v f'$. For S dynamical plasma species and a fixed background, the system can be written as

$$\frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial \mathbf{r}} + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot \frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = C[f^{(s)}] \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, S \quad (3.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0 \int d^3v' \mathbf{v}' \left(\sum_{s'=1}^S q_{s'} f^{(s')} + q' f' \right) + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon_0} \int d^3v' \left(\sum_{s'=1}^S q_{s'} f^{(s')} + q' f' \right) \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

where q_s, q' are the charges as well as $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ are the electric and magnetic fields, respectively. Note that the charge and current densities were expressed from the distribution functions. Also note that to avoid ambiguity, we use dummy species label s'

and dummy velocity label v' in (3.3). The model has a quadratic nonlinearity, since the fields, which are linear in the distribution functions $\{f^{(s)}\}$, are dotted with $\partial f^{(s)}/\partial \mathbf{v}$ in (3.2).

3.1.2 (1+1) dimensional model

The full Vlasov-Maxwell system is formulated on the (3 + 3) phase space. In the following analysis, we focus on a simplified case and solve it in (1 + 1) dimensions, which can be viewed as invariance with respect to the other (2 + 2) dimensions. In this case (3.2-3.3) simplify to

$$\frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial x} + \frac{q_s}{m_s} E \frac{\partial f^{(s)}}{\partial v} = C[f^{(s)}] \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, S \quad (3.4)$$

as well as a coupling equation between $f^{(s)}(x, v, t)$ and $E(x, t)$. This can either be Gauss's or Ampere's law:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_0} \int dv' \left(\sum_{s'=1}^S q_{s'} f^{(s')} + q' f' \right) \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\varepsilon_0} \int dv' v' \left(\sum_{s'=1}^S q_{s'} f^{(s')} + q' f' \right). \quad (3.5)$$

Note that the self-generated magnetic field does not appear in one dimension and also that the integrations are not explicitly written out for the other (2 + 2) dimensions as they have no effect. We shall compute E from Gauss's law and not evolve it in time as an independent dynamic function, which would be the case with Ampere's law. Justification for this choice is discussed in Appendix B.

While the above model is the subject of Chapter 7, Chapters 5-6 focus on *one dynamical species* made up of electrons (e) with the same number of ions (i) creating a fixed background. This background is taken to be simply ionized, i.e. $q' = +e$, and uniformly distributed in position space. The number densities are $n_{(e)}(x)$ and $n'(x) = n'$, respectively, and they are set such that the plasma is overall neutral. The resulting system, dropping the (e) superscript from $f^{(e)}$ and m_e , is formulated as

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \frac{e^2}{m\varepsilon_0} \frac{\partial f}{\partial v} \int^x dx' \int dv' (f' - f) = C[f]. \quad (3.6)$$

This will be used as a starting point for later calculations. Note that the first integral is cumulative in x and comes from Gauss's law. The second one is over the whole range of v values.

3.2 Collision operator

The role of the collision operator is to mimic the effect of microscopic collisions between particles, on the evolution of the distribution functions. Commonly used collision operators include the simple Krook operator [27] and the more sophisticated Fokker-Planck operator [28]. In this work a generalized version of the Krook collision operator is used, given by

$$C[f^{(s)}] = \nu^{(s)}(v) (f^{M,(s)} - f^{(s)}), \quad (3.7)$$

where $\nu^{(s)}(v)$ is a velocity dependent collision frequency and $f^{M,(s)} = f^{M,(s)}(v) \sim \exp(-b_s v^2)$ is a Maxwellian distribution, which is also a Gaussian in one dimension. Both can vary across different species, hence the label s . To simplify the model, we shall not take into account inter-species collisions. The Krook collision operator pushes $f^{(s)}$ into $f^{M,(s)}$, the equilibrium

state, over timescale $1/\nu^{(s)}(v)$. Note that physically, the b_s parameter can be expressed as $b_s = m_s/(2k_B T_s)$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T_s is the temperature of species s .

The velocity dependence of $\nu^{(s)}(v)$ in the Krook model was proposed in [29] and further investigated in [30, 31]. The conclusion is that by enforcing certain conditions on the functions $\nu^{(s)}(v)$, the Krook operator can mimic the behaviour of the physically more meaningful Fokker–Planck operator despite being more simple. Furthermore, this can be done while maintaining some desired properties of the system such as the conservation of particle number, total momentum and energy.

For our analysis, we take the following very general polynomial form for $\nu^{(s)}(v)$:

$$\nu^{(s)}(v) = \nu_0^{(s)} + \sum_{k=1}^K \nu_k^{(s)} |v|^k, \quad (3.8)$$

for some K . We furthermore require $\nu_0^{(s)} > 0$ and $\nu_k^{(s)} \geq 0$ for $k \geq 1$. This form is chosen such that $\min_v \nu^{(s)}(v) = \nu_0^{(s)} > 0$, which will be required in proving the convergence of the quantum algorithm, and such that it can be linearly upper bounded on the region $-v_{\max} \leq v \leq v_{\max}$ as

$$\nu^{(s)}(v) \leq \frac{\nu^{(s)}(v_{\max}) - \nu_0^{(s)}}{v_{\max}} |v| + \nu_0^{(s)}. \quad (3.9)$$

This property will also be utilized later. Notice how $\nu^{(s)}(v)$ monotonically increases as the magnitude of the microscopic velocity $|v|$ increases, as it is intuitively expected from the nature of collisions. This enables faster particles to relax to $f^{M,(s)}$ more rapidly than slow ones.

3.3 Discretization scheme

3.3.1 Discretizing the coordinates

The distribution functions $f^{(s)}(x, v, t)$ have to be discretized to formulate the problem as an ODE system. To do so, we put them on a 2 dimensional grid of size (N_x, N_v) and represent them as a matrix as

$$f^{(s)} = \begin{pmatrix} f_{1,1}^{(s)} & f_{1,2}^{(s)} & \cdots & f_{1,N_v}^{(s)} \\ f_{2,1}^{(s)} & f_{2,2}^{(s)} & \cdots & f_{2,N_v}^{(s)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{N_x,1}^{(s)} & f_{N_x,2}^{(s)} & \cdots & f_{N_x,N_v}^{(s)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.10)$$

where the elements mean $f_{i,j}^{(s)} = f^{(s)}(x_i, v_j, t)$ with discrete position and velocity coordinates x_i and v_j , respectively. The above expression is referred to as the *distribution matrix*. Each species s has its own $f^{(s)}$. The mentioned discretized coordinates are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &= -x_{\max} + (i-1)\Delta x & \text{with} & & 1 \leq i \leq N_x, \\ \text{such that} & & -x_{\max} \leq x_i \leq x_{\max} & \text{and} & x_{\max} = \frac{(N_x-1)\Delta x}{2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} v_j &= -v_{\max} + (j-1)\Delta v & \text{with} & & 1 \leq j \leq N_v, \\ \text{such that} & & -v_{\max} \leq v_j \leq v_{\max} & \text{and} & v_{\max} = \frac{(N_v-1)\Delta v}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

Note that $x_i > 0$ for $i > \lceil N_x/2 \rceil$ as well as that $x_i \leq 0$ for $i \leq \lceil N_x/2 \rceil$, and similarly for v_j . We define $N = N_x N_v$ as the total number of gridpoints.

3.3.2 Boundary conditions

There is a freedom in choosing boundary conditions (BCs). For the distribution functions $f^{(s)}(x, v, t)$, we adopt periodic BCs in space and fixed ones in velocity. Additionally, the lower bound of the cumulative x integral for the expression of $E(x)$ is taken to be $-x_{\max}$ in (3.5-3.6). Hence,

$$f(-x_{\max}, v, t) = f(x_{\max} + \Delta x, v, t) \quad \forall v, t \quad (3.13a)$$

$$f(x, -v_{\max} - \Delta v, t) = f(x, v_{\max} + \Delta v, t) = 0 \quad \forall x, t \quad (3.13b)$$

$$E(-x_{\max}, t) = 0 \quad \forall t. \quad (3.13c)$$

The species label s was not written out explicitly as we take the same BCs for all species.

3.3.3 Discrete calculus

The discretization of derivatives and integrals introduces an error on $\partial f_{ij}/\partial t$ that scales with the increments $\Delta x, \Delta v$. We choose to work with first order schemes, meaning an error of $\mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2 + \Delta v^2) = \mathcal{O}(N_x^{-2} + N_v^{-2})$ as $N_x, N_v \gg 1$. In this subsection as well, we drop the species label s and take the same scheme for all species.

The derivatives are approximated with central difference schemes as

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right|_{ij} f = -\frac{1}{2\Delta x} \begin{cases} f_{i+1,j} - f_{i+N_x-1,j} & \text{for } i = 1 \\ f_{i-N_x+1,j} - f_{i-1,j} & \text{for } i = N_x \\ f_{i+1,j} - f_{i-1,j} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \right|_{ij} f = -\frac{1}{2\Delta v} \begin{cases} f_{i,j+1} & \text{for } j = 1 \\ -f_{i,j-1} & \text{for } j = N_v \\ f_{i,j+1} - f_{i,j-1} & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (3.15)$$

where the different cases arise due to the specific BCs from (3.13a-3.13b). We choose these due to their stability and symmetry.

The double integral, that is cumulative in x and goes over the whole range of v , is approximated with the 2 dimensional trapezoidal rule [32], given by

$$\iint^{x_i} f(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J = \frac{\Delta x \Delta v}{4} \cdot \begin{cases} \left\{ 0 \right. & \text{for } i = 1 \\ \left\{ \begin{aligned} & f_{1,1} + f_{i,1} + f_{1,N_v} + f_{i,N_v} \\ & + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{i-1} f_{I,1} + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{i-1} f_{I,N_v} \\ & + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v-1} f_{1,J} + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v-1} f_{i,J} + 4 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v-1} \sum_{I=2}^{i-1} f_{I,J} \end{aligned} \right. & \text{for } 2 \leq i \leq N_x, \end{cases} \quad (3.16)$$

in which the corners of the grid have weight 1, the edges have weight 2 and the inner bulk elements have weight 4. Note that the equation has i as a free index while I and J are dummy indices in position and velocity, respectively. Also, due to the BC, (3.13c), for $i = 1$ no integral is performed. For $i = 2$ there are no bulk terms, meaning that the double sum term vanishes. This weighting is illustrated with a concrete example in Fig. 3.1.

These weightings imposed on the elements of f by the finite difference derivatives and integrals are commonly known as stencils. Note that in order for the discrete derivatives and integral above to work, we require $N_x, N_v \geq 3$.

1	2	2	2	1
2	4	4	4	2
2	4	4	4	2
2	4	4	4	2
1	2	2	2	1
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0

Figure 3.1: An example of the weighting applied to the elements of f , set by the 2 dimensional trapezoidal rule from (3.16). This example is for a $(N_x, N_v) = (7, 5)$ grid and $i = 5$.

3.3.4 Finite difference equation

Applying the above discretization of (3.14-3.16) to (3.4-3.5), as well as the generalized Krook operator from (3.7), one obtains the finite difference equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} f_{ij}^{(s)} = - \frac{q_s}{m_s \varepsilon_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \Big|_{ij} f^{(s)} \cdot \sum_{s'=1}^S q_{s'} \iint^{x_i} f^{(s')}(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J \quad \mathcal{O} \left([f^{(s)}]^2 \right) \quad (3.17a)$$

$$- v_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Big|_{ij} f^{(s)} - \frac{q_s q'}{m_s \varepsilon_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \Big|_{ij} f^{(s)} \cdot \iint^{x_i} f'(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J \quad \mathcal{O} \left([f^{(s)}]^1 \right) \quad (3.17b)$$

$$- \nu^{(s)}(v_j) f_{ij}^{(s)} \quad \mathcal{O} \left([f^{(s)}]^1 \right) \quad (3.17c)$$

$$+ \nu^{(s)}(v_j) f_j^{M,(s)}, \quad \mathcal{O} \left([f^{(s)}]^0 \right) \quad (3.17d)$$

where the discretized target Maxwellian is

$$f_j^{M,(s)} = \frac{\mathcal{N}_s}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \left[\sum_{J=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-b_s v_J^2) \right]^{-1} \exp(-b_s v_j^2). \quad (3.18)$$

The prefactor in the above equation ensures that $\iint f^{(s)} dx dv = \mathcal{N}_s$ under the trapezoidal rule for the integration on the whole grid, where \mathcal{N}_s is the number of s -species particles per unit area of the other 2 position dimensions. Said otherwise, $\mathcal{N}_s = \int n_s(x) dx$. The discretization introduces an error of $\mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2 + \Delta v^2)$ on $\partial f_{ij}^{(s)} / \partial t$. Note that by assuming that the static background is uniform in space, i.e. $f'(x_I, v_J) = f'(v_J)$, the integral in (3.17b) becomes

$$\iint^{x_i} f'(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J = \frac{i-1}{N_x-1} \mathcal{N}', \quad (3.19)$$

where $\mathcal{N}' = \int n' dx = n' \cdot 2x_{\max}$ is the number of background particles per unit area of the other 2 position dimensions.

Chapter 7 focuses on mapping (3.17a-3.17d) onto the quantum algorithm. Chapters 5-6 are concerned with the simplified case, that only has one dynamical species, i.e. electrons (e), and a singly ionized static background. The continuous version of that was given in (3.6), which,

under the discretization scheme, becomes

$$\frac{d}{dt}f_{ij} = -\frac{e^2}{m\varepsilon_0}\frac{\partial}{\partial v}\Big|_{ij} f \cdot \iint^{x_i} f(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J \quad \mathcal{O}(f^2) \quad (3.20a)$$

$$-v_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x}\Big|_{ij} f + \frac{e^2}{m\varepsilon_0}\frac{\partial}{\partial v}\Big|_{ij} f \cdot \iint^{x_i} f'(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J \quad \mathcal{O}(f^1) \quad (3.20b)$$

$$-\nu(v_j)f_{ij} \quad \mathcal{O}(f^1) \quad (3.20c)$$

$$+\nu(v_j)f_j^M, \quad \mathcal{O}(f^0) \quad (3.20d)$$

where the discretized target Maxwellian is

$$f_j^M = \frac{\mathcal{N}}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \left[\sum_{J=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-bv_J^2) \right]^{-1} \exp(-bv_j^2). \quad (3.21)$$

Note that the single species label (e) was dropped for readability. Also note that (3.19) still holds.

3.4 Physical scenario

A real life plasma that approximately satisfies our BCs is the astrophysical plasma within interstellar medium. Furthermore, the (1+1) dimensional approximation is relatively accurate when considering the flow of ionized matter far from its sources. The concrete example we shall use later for *one* dynamical species is warm ionized medium (WIM) made up of electrons and ionized hydrogen, which takes up 20-50 % of the interstellar matter of the Milky way. Its typical parameters are [33]:

$$T = 8000 \text{ K}, \quad \bar{n} = \bar{n}' = 5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^{-3}, \quad (3.22)$$

where $\bar{n} = \bar{n}'$ is the *average* number density in position space. Additionally, we choose

$$x_{\max} = 1000 \text{ km}, \quad v_{\max} = 10 \cdot v_p, \quad (3.23)$$

with $v_p = 1/\sqrt{b}$ being the most probable velocity and $b = m/(2k_B T)$ being the decay factor of the Maxwellian. Then for simulations we shall choose $n' = \bar{n}'$ and $n(x)$ such that $\int n(x) dx = \bar{n} \cdot 2x_{\max}$, hence $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N}' = \bar{n} \cdot 2x_{\max}$. For later comparison we mention that typically the collision frequency is approximately [11]:

$$\nu_0 \approx \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{e^4 \bar{n}}{\varepsilon_0^2 m^2 v_p^3}\right) \approx 4 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}. \quad (3.24)$$

Chapter 4

The quantum algorithm

Essentially, a quantum algorithm on a digital quantum computer is a sequence of single- and multiple-qubit unitary gates (operations) as well as measurements on qubits. This sequence itself is a unitary operation done on the state of the quantum computer that mimics the solution of the Schrödinger equation, i.e. $|\Psi(t)\rangle = \hat{U}|\Psi(0)\rangle$ with \hat{U} being unitary. The runtime of a quantum algorithm is measured by its gate complexity, the quantum analogue of the classical time complexity. That is the asymptotic scaling of the runtime with respect to free parameters of the problem solved.

4.1 Problem statement

The quantum algorithm, onto which the discretized Vlasov equation is mapped, was developed recently by Krovi in [26]. Its input is a d dimensional ODE system in the form

$$\frac{d\vec{u}}{dt} = F^{(2)}\vec{u}^{\otimes 2} + F^{(1)}\vec{u} + F^{(0)}, \quad \vec{u}(0) = \vec{u}_{\text{in}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where the state vector $\vec{u} = [u_1, \dots, u_d]^T \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a d dimensional column vector and $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2} = \vec{u} \otimes \vec{u} = [u_1^2, u_1u_2, \dots, u_1u_d, u_2u_1, \dots, u_du_{d-1}, u_d^2]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$ is a d^2 dimensional column vector containing all the quadratic nonlinearities. Each $u_k = u_k(t)$ is a function of time t on the interval $t \in [0, T]$. The 3 matrices $F^{(2)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d^2 \times d^2}$, $F^{(1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ and $F^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ (which is a vector) are *all time independent* and have sizes such that the matrix multiplication in (4.1) makes sense. All terms above are real.

Note that the other quantum algorithms based on numerical linearization mentioned earlier have similar, but slightly different inputs to (4.1) and hence cannot be applied to solve systems (3.17a-3.17d) and (3.20a-3.20d). To be exact, [22, 24] requires $F^{(0)} = 0$ and [23] requires $F^{(0)} = F^{(0)}(t)$, i.e. an explicit time dependence in the inhomogeneous term. This would correspond to an explicit time dependence in the target Maxwellian in the collision operator, i.e. $f^{M,(s)}(v) \rightarrow f^{M,(s)}(v, t)$. Finally, the one in [25] is similar to that in [26] but it is concerned with higher dimensional nonlinearities.

4.2 Convergence criteria

The simplicity of the input (4.1) of this quantum algorithm comes at a cost in the form of certain constraints. Firstly, $F^{(1)}$ must have a negative log-norm:

$$\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0, \quad (4.2)$$

which is related to it being dissipative. Secondly, it is required that $R < 1$ for the convergence parameter R , given by

$$R = \frac{1}{|\mu(F^{(1)})|} \left(\|F^{(2)}\| \|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\| + \frac{\|F^{(0)}\|}{\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|} \right), \quad (4.3)$$

where the vector norms $\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$, $\|F^{(0)}\|$ denote the l_2 norm and $\|F^{(2)}\|$ denotes the spectral norm. This quantifies how strong the nonlinear and inhomogeneous effects are compared to the linear dissipation.

4.3 The algorithm

Below the quantum algorithm is briefly outlined. Further details are given in [26] but are not necessary to understand this project.

4.3.1 Input

The input consists of maps for the elements of each expression in (4.1), after being rescaled using the norm of the initial condition. The state vector is rescaled as $\vec{u} \rightarrow \vec{u}/\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ and the matrices $F^{(2)}$, $F^{(0)}$ as $F^{(2)} \rightarrow F^{(2)}\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$, $F^{(0)} \rightarrow F^{(0)}/\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$. Note that this rescaling does *not* affect $F^{(1)}$ and R .

4.3.2 Computational steps

1. The first step is performing Carleman linearization on the system. That linearized system has a state vector \vec{x} , given by

$$\vec{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{u} \\ \vec{u}^{\otimes 2} \\ \vdots \\ \vec{u}^{\otimes N_C} \end{bmatrix} = [\vec{u}^T; \vec{u}^{\otimes 2 T}; \dots; \vec{u}^{\otimes N_C T}]^T, \quad (4.4)$$

where N_C is the number of Carleman linearization steps. This vector is evolved by the linear equation

$$\frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} = A\vec{x} + \vec{b}, \quad \vec{x}(0) = [\vec{u}_{\text{in}}^T; \vec{u}_{\text{in}}^{\otimes 2 T}; \dots; \vec{u}_{\text{in}}^{\otimes N_C T}]^T. \quad (4.5)$$

For $N_C \rightarrow \infty$, (4.5) not only approximates (4.1), but exactly encodes it. A and \vec{b} can be constructed from $F^{(2)}$, $F^{(1)}$ and $F^{(0)}$.

2. The second step is discretizing time with increments Δt , such that $t_i = i\Delta t$ and $i \in \{0, \dots, T/\Delta t\}$, assuming that $T/\Delta t$ is an integer. That transforms (4.5) into

$$L|y\rangle = |\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle, \quad (4.6)$$

which is a linear system of (algebraic) equations.

3. The last step is inverting (4.6) using a quantum linear system algorithm (QLSA) to obtain the vector (a quantum state)

$$|y\rangle = L^{-1}|\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle. \quad (4.7)$$

4.3.3 Output

The above steps output the quantum state $|y\rangle$, which is a superposition of $y_{T/\Delta t}$ states and y_i states with $i < T/\Delta t$. Note that $y_{T/\Delta t}$ encodes all the information about $\vec{x}(T)$ and hence $\vec{u}(T)$. The probability to recover $y_{T/\Delta t}$ by measuring $|y\rangle$ is lower bounded as

$$P[\text{measuring } y_{T/\Delta t}] \geq \frac{1}{18g^2}, \quad \text{where} \quad g = \frac{\max_{t \in \{0, T\}} \|\vec{x}(t)\|}{\|\vec{x}(T)\|}. \quad (4.8)$$

This is increased within the quantum algorithm with amplitude amplification [34].

4.4 Gate complexity

If both $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$ and $R < 1$ are satisfied, then the quantum algorithm, including the amplitude amplification, is guaranteed to solve (4.1) with gate complexity

$$\mathcal{O}\left(g_u T \|A\| \text{poly}(N_C, s)\right) \quad \cdot \quad \text{weak logarithmic dependencies}, \quad (4.9)$$

where

$$g_u = \frac{\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|}{\|\vec{u}(T)\|} \quad (4.10)$$

and

$$N_C = \left\lceil \frac{2 \log(T \|F^{(2)}\| / \delta \|\vec{u}(T)\|)}{\log(1 / \|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|)} \right\rceil, \quad (4.11)$$

with δ being the error on the solution. Furthermore, s denotes the sparsity of $F^{(2)}, F^{(1)}, F^{(0)}$, i.e. they have at most s nonzero entries in each row and column. The expression $\text{poly}(\cdot, \cdot)$ means a polynomial of its inputs. The weak logarithmic dependencies include dependencies on $T, \|F^{(0)}\|, \|A\|, d$ and $1/\epsilon$, where ϵ is the allowed fractional error on the solution and is connected to δ . $\|A\|$ satisfies

$$\|A\| \leq N_C (\|F^{(0)}\| + \|F^{(1)}\| + \|F^{(2)}\|). \quad (4.12)$$

All matrices above have dimension $1/\text{time}$ due to the rescaling $\vec{u} \rightarrow \vec{u}/\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$.

Chapter 5

Mapping for 1 species

This section is concerned with mapping the $(1+1)$ dimensional discretized Vlasov equation with one dynamical species, as formulated in (3.20a-3.20d), onto (4.1), the input of the quantum algorithm. As mentioned before the one dynamical species is taken to be electrons and the static background is taken to be singly positively ionized with charge $+e$. The species label (e) is dropped in this chapter.

5.1 Vectorization of the distribution matrix

5.1.1 \vec{u}

Firstly, the state vector \vec{u} is constructed from the *vectorization* of the distribution matrix f from (3.10) as

$$\vec{u} = \text{vec}(f) = \text{vec} \begin{pmatrix} f_{1,1} & f_{1,2} & \cdots & f_{1,N_v} \\ f_{2,1} & f_{2,2} & \cdots & f_{2,N_v} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{N_x,1} & f_{N_x,2} & \cdots & f_{N_x,N_v} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{1,1} \\ f_{1,2} \\ \vdots \\ f_{1,N_v} \\ f_{2,1} \\ \vdots \\ f_{2,N_v} \\ \vdots \\ f_{N_x,N_v} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.1)$$

Note that \vec{u} has length $N = N_x N_v$. Elements of \vec{u} can be expressed from those of f and vice versa as

$$u_n = f_{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor, n \parallel N_v}, \quad \text{where } \underbrace{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor}_{\text{computes row index } i}, \quad \underbrace{n \parallel N_v}_{\text{computes column index } j} \quad (5.2)$$

$$f_{ij} = u_{(i-1)N_v + j}, \quad \text{where } \underbrace{(i-1)N_v}_{\text{goes over } i-1 \text{ full rows}}, \quad \underbrace{j}_{\text{gives } j\text{-th element of row } i}, \quad (5.3)$$

where the double slash notation was defined in Table 2.1. Hence the index n entirely identifies the tuple (i, j) and vice versa.

5.1.2 $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$

Then, $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ becomes

$$\vec{u}^{\otimes 2} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{1,1}\vec{u} \\ f_{1,2}\vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ f_{1,N_v}\vec{u} \\ f_{2,1}\vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ f_{2,N_v}\vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ f_{N_x,N_v}\vec{u} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.4)$$

where each ‘element’ above is an N dimensional vector. For example, the first one reads $f_{11}\vec{u} = [f_{11}u_1, f_{11}u_2, \dots, f_{11}u_n]^T$. Hence, $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ is N^2 dimensional. Its elements can be associated to those of \vec{u} and f , and vice versa, via

$$u_n^{\otimes 2} = u_{\lfloor n/N \rfloor} \cdot u_{n \// N}, \quad \text{where } \underbrace{\lfloor n/N \rfloor}_{\text{gives first term of product}}, \quad \underbrace{n \// N}_{\text{gives second term of product}} \quad (5.5)$$

$$u_a \cdot u_b = u_{N(a-1)+b}^{\otimes 2}, \quad \text{where } \underbrace{N(a-1)}_{\text{goes over terms } u_1\vec{u}, \dots, u_{a-1}\vec{u}}, \quad \underbrace{b}_{\text{gives } b\text{-th element of } u_a\vec{u}} \quad (5.6)$$

$$f_{ab} \cdot f_{cd} = u_{N[(a-1)N_v+b-1]+(c-1)N_v+d}^{\otimes 2}, \quad \text{where } \underbrace{N[(a-1)N_v+b-1]}_{\text{goes over terms } f_{1,1}\vec{u}, \dots, f_{a,b-1}\vec{u}}, \quad \underbrace{(c-1)N_v+d}_{\text{gives correct element within } f_{a,b}\vec{u}} \quad (5.7)$$

Note that (5.6-5.7) are not unique since the Kronecker product places each $f_{ab} \cdot f_{cd}$ term twice into $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$, except the square terms with $(a, b) = (c, d)$. The above formulas can be realized from the structure of the Kronecker product and \vec{u} .

5.2 Finding the matrices

5.2.1 General method

The elements of $F^{(0)}$, $F^{(1)}$ and $F^{(2)}$ can be extracted from the finite difference equation *procedurally*. Below we outline a general technique to perform this procedure, that can be applied to any finite difference scheme that evolves an object with 2 indices (a matrix) and has a quadratic nonlinearity.

Step 0:

One has to realize the finite difference equation, in this case given by (3.20a-3.20d), in the schematic form

$$\frac{d}{dt} f_{ij} = \sum_{(I,J;I',J') \in Z^{(ij)(2)}} K_{IJ;I'J'}^{(ij)(2)} f_{IJ} f_{I'J'} + \sum_{(I,J) \in Z^{(ij)(1)}} K_{IJ}^{(ij)(1)} f_{IJ} + \sum_{m \in Z^{(ij)(0)}} K_m^{(ij)(0)}. \quad (5.8)$$

The first sum encodes (3.20a), the nonlinear part of the evolution; the second sum encodes (3.20b-3.20c), the linear part; while the last one encodes (3.20d), the inhomogeneity. The sets

$Z^{(ij)(2)}$, $Z^{(ij)(1)}$ and $Z^{(ij)(0)}$ simply *bookkeep* which terms appear in the finite difference equation. $Z^{(ij)(2)}$ and $Z^{(ij)(1)}$ contain all tuples (I, J, I', J') and (I, J) that appear, respectively. $Z^{(ij)(0)}$ bookkeeps the inhomogeneous terms and is slightly different, as it contains simple indices m instead of tuples of indices. Note that these sets are different for different matrix elements f_{ij} , hence the (ij) label. The coefficients $K_{IJ;I'J'}^{(ij)(2)}$ and $K_{IJ}^{(ij)(1)}$ introduce a weighting for the elements of the matrix f and also explicitly depend on i and j . This dependence also appears in $K_m^{(ij)(0)}$. These coefficients encode all the information about the discretization scheme such as the stencils. The indices i, j are free while I, J, I', J' are dummy. Note that one does not need to do anything to get (5.8), since schemes such as (3.20a-3.20d) are already in this form.

Step 1:

First, one has to substitute the conversion formulas, (5.3) and (5.7). Since terms of the form $f_{IJ}f_{I'J'}$ can be expressed as elements of $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ and those of the form f_{IJ} as elements of \vec{u} , the substitution results in an evolution equation of the form

$$\frac{du_n}{dt} = \sum_{m \in S^{(n)(2)}} C_m^{(n)(2)} u_m^{\otimes 2} + \sum_{m \in S^{(n)(1)}} C_m^{(n)(1)} u_m + \sum_{m \in S^{(n)(0)}} C_m^{(n)(0)}, \quad (5.9)$$

with coefficients $C_m^{(n)(2)}$, $C_m^{(n)(1)}$, $C_m^{(n)(0)}$. The first two encode a *weighting* for the elements of $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ and \vec{u} , respectively, while $C_m^{(n)(0)}$ encodes the inhomogeneity. These contain the same information as $K_{IJ;I'J'}^{(ij)(2)}$, $K_{IJ}^{(ij)(1)}$ and $K_m^{(ij)(0)}$, respectively. The sets $S^{(n)(2)}$ and $S^{(n)(1)}$ describe *which elements* of the mentioned vectors take part in evolving u_n . The superscript (n) is associated with the superscripts (ij) via $n = (i-1)N_v + j$. These superscript indices denote which element of \vec{u} is being evolved. Hence, the ij dependence of the K coefficients and the sets Z become the n dependence of the C coefficients and the sets S . Note that this substitution also includes using the formulas $i = \lceil n/N_v \rceil$ and $j = n \parallel N_v$, so n is the only free index and m is a dummy one.

Step 2:

The key point to realize is that the above sums are essentially *linear combinations* of the elements of $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ and \vec{u} . These linear combinations can be identified as *matrix multiplications* with suitable matrices $F^{(2)}$ and $F^{(1)}$. By also denoting the inhomogeneous terms with a matrix (a vector to be exact), called $F^{(0)}$, one obtains

$$\frac{du_n}{dt} = \sum_{k=1}^{d^2} F_{nk}^{(2)} u_k^{\otimes 2} + \sum_{k=1}^d F_{nk}^{(1)} u_k + F_n^{(0)}, \quad (5.10)$$

or equivalently

$$\frac{d\vec{u}}{dt} = F^{(2)} \vec{u}^{\otimes 2} + F^{(1)} \vec{u} + F^{(0)}. \quad (5.11)$$

Step 3:

Finally, by comparing (5.9) with (5.10), one may realize that the elements of the matrices $F^{(2)}$, $F^{(1)}$, $F^{(0)}$ must satisfy

$$F_{nk}^{(2)} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{S}^{(n)(2)}} C_m^{(n)(2)} \delta_{km} \quad (5.12)$$

$$F_{nk}^{(1)} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{S}^{(n)(1)}} C_m^{(n)(1)} \delta_{km} \quad (5.13)$$

$$F_n^{(0)} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{S}^{(n)(0)}} C_m^{(n)(0)}, \quad (5.14)$$

since the deltas cancel the sums over the k 's. Hence, a map for the elements of the matrices can be extracted from the finite difference scheme. We now apply this scheme to (3.20a-3.20d).

Checking

We note that after doing the above procedure, one can numerically verify if the obtained matrices $F^{(2)}$, $F^{(1)}$, $F^{(0)}$ are correct. One needs to choose some matrix f , compute the matrix df/dt using the finite difference equation, and then compare $\text{vec}(df/dt)$ with $d\vec{u}/dt = F^{(2)}\vec{u}^{\otimes 2} + F^{(1)}\vec{u} + F^{(0)}$, where $\vec{u} = \text{vec}(f)$. For random f matrices they are equal if the mapping is correct. This works because vectorization and time differentiation commute, i.e. $\text{vec}(df/dt) = d[\text{vec}(f)]/dt$.

5.2.2 $F^{(0)}$

From (3.20d), we realize the elements of $F^{(0)}$ as

$$F_n^{(0)} = \frac{\mathcal{N}}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-bv_j^2) \right]^{-1} \cdot \nu(v_{n//N_v}) \exp(-bv_{n//N_v}^2), \quad (5.15)$$

where the normalized Maxwellian was substituted from (3.21). Note that the n dependence on the RHS only appears in the form of $n // N_v = j$ as expected from a collision operator without x dependence.

5.2.3 $F^{(1)}$

The linear contribution is partitioned into two parts as $F^{(1)} = \hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)}$. Let $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ encode the collisional part of the linear evolution, (3.20c), and $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ encode the rest of the linear contributions, (3.20b).

Therefore,

$$\bar{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = -\nu(v_{n//N_v}) \delta_{k,n}, \quad (5.16)$$

where the $\delta_{k,n}$ encodes the proportionality with f_{ij} . Hence $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ is diagonal.

For $\hat{F}^{(1)}$, the elements read

$$\hat{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = -\frac{v_{n//N_v}}{2\Delta x} \begin{cases} \delta_{k,n+N_v} - \delta_{k,n+N_v(N_x-1)} & \text{for } n \leq N_v \\ \delta_{k,n+N_v} - \delta_{k,n-N_v} & \text{for } N_v < n \leq N_v(N_x-1) \\ \delta_{k,n-N_v(N_x-1)} - \delta_{k,n-N_v} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (5.17a)$$

$$+ \frac{e^2 \mathcal{N}}{2m\varepsilon_0 \Delta v} \frac{[n/N_v] - 1}{N_x - 1} \begin{cases} \delta_{k,n+1} & \text{for } n // N_v = 1 \\ -\delta_{k,n-1} & \text{for } n // N_v = N_v \\ \delta_{k,n+1} - \delta_{k,n-1} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (5.17b)$$

The first term encodes $-v_j \partial/\partial x|_{ij} f$ and has 3 cases, which are equivalent to the 3 cases of (3.14), the discretized derivative operator. The second term encodes $(e^2/m\varepsilon_0) \partial/\partial v|_{ij} f \cdot \iint^{x_i} f'(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J$, in which the value of the integral was substituted from (3.19). Note how $\lceil n/N_v \rceil$ computes i . The cases arise from the cases of (3.15), the discretized derivative operator.

A very important property of $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ is that it is antisymmetric, otherwise known as skew-symmetric, i.e. $\hat{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = -\hat{F}_{k,n}^{(1)}$. This arises due to the symmetric structure of the center difference derivatives as well as that of the BCs. It is also entirely off-diagonal.

The structure of $F^{(1)}$ can be illustrated well by separating out the terms in the matrix based on what physical effect they represent. See Fig. 5.1 for an example of this illustration, for a $(4, 4)$ grid. The red elements come from the collision operator and are diagonal; while the blue and green elements come from the non-collisional linear part of the Vlasov equation and are off-diagonal. Note that sites with the same colour do not necessarily have the same numerical value. Each u_n is evolved by the sum of the elements of \vec{u} , weighted by the $n = [(i-1)N_v + j]$ -th row of the matrix.

Figure 5.1: An example of the $F^{(1)}$ matrix for a $(4, 4)$ grid. On the left, the evolved vector \vec{u} is written out explicitly, its length is $N = 16$. The middle matrix is $F^{(1)} = \hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)}$. It contains 3 kinds of elements, denoted by 3 colours, as indicated on the right. Gray elements are 0. Some elements have value 0 because of the BCs. The vector on the top is also \vec{u} and it represents how the matrix multiplication mixes its elements.

The blue elements encode (5.17a). They are $N_x = 4$ sites away from the diagonal both to the left and the right generally, since elements of f with first indices $i \pm 1$ and same second indices j are $N_x = 4$ apart in \vec{u} due to the structure of the row-major vectorization. The exception is when $i = 1$ or $i = N_x = 4$, because then due to the periodic BCs, (3.13a), one of the elements appearing in $\partial/\partial x|_{ij} f$ is $N_v(N_x - 1) = 12$ further away from the diagonal.

The green elements encode (5.17b). They are directly above and below the diagonal, since elements of f with the same first indices i but differing second indices $j \pm 1$ are placed 2 apart in \vec{u} . The sites in the first $N_x = 4$ rows have value 0 since $\iint^{x_1} f' = 0$, as given by the electric field BC in (3.13c). The sites on the left of the diagonal for the $j = 1$ rows as well as those on the right of the diagonal for the $j = N_v = 4$ rows also have values of 0 because of (3.13b), the BCs in velocity. One of the ‘legs’ of $\partial/\partial v|_{ij}$ vanish in these cases.

5.2.4 $F^{(2)}$

The map for $F_{nk}^{(2)}$ can be obtained with brute force based on the general procedure. We provide an expression for it in Appendix A. Here, we construct the matrix in a physically more intuitive and meaningful way.

The building unit of $F^{(2)}$ is the trapezoidal rule row vector, denoted by \mathbb{T} , that contains all the information about the trapezoidal rule. Just as the scheme in (3.16), $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ carries a free index i , which is the last position index still being integrated over. Mathematically, it reads

$$\mathbb{T}^{[i]} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left\{ T \text{vec}(0_{N_x, N_v}) = \underbrace{[0, 0, \dots, 0]}_{N_x N_v \text{ times}} \right. \quad \text{for } i = 1 \\ \left. \left\{ T \text{vec} \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} 1 & 2 & \cdots & 2 & 1 \\ 2 & 4 & \cdots & 4 & 2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 2 & 4 & \cdots & 4 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & \cdots & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right] \right\} \quad \begin{array}{l} i \text{ rows} \\ \\ \\ N_x - i \text{ rows} \end{array} \\ \left. \right\} \quad \text{for } i > 1. \end{array} \right. \\ = [1, \underbrace{2, \dots, 2}_{N_v-2 \text{ times}}, 1, \underbrace{(2, \underbrace{4, \dots, 4}_{N_v-2 \text{ times}}, 2)}_{N_v-2 \text{ times}}, \dots, \underbrace{(2, \underbrace{4, \dots, 4}_{N_v-2 \text{ times}}, 2)}_{N_v-2 \text{ times}}, 1, \underbrace{2, \dots, 2}_{N_v-2 \text{ times}}, 1, \underbrace{0, \dots, 0}_{(N_x-i)N_v \text{ times}}] \quad (5.18)$$

Here T denotes the transpose operation and is put to the front of the vectorization for readability. The matrix that is being vectorized has 1’s in the corners, 2’s on the edges and 4’s on the inside, while 0’s on the slots that do not take part in the integration. This is the same structure that was shown on Fig. 3.1. For $i = 1$, all slots are 0, hence $\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$ is just a vector of 0’s. For all i , $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ is row vector of length N .

The point of this object is that the electric field generated by the electrons at position x_i can be computed by matrix multiplying $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ by \vec{u} as

$$E(x_i)^{(e)} \propto \iint^{x_i} f(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J = \frac{\Delta x \Delta v}{4} \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \vec{u}. \quad (5.19)$$

See (3.5, 3.20a) for why the above integral computes the field. Essentially this multiplication applies the weighting of the trapezoidal rule to the elements u_n and sums up the result.

From such building units the $F^{(2)}$ matrix can be constructed. Let us first consider an explicit example for a (3, 4) grid, as shown on Fig. 5.2. u_n is evolved by the sum of the elements of $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$, weighted by the $n = [(i-1)N_v + j]$ -th row of $F^{(2)}$. The size of $F^{(2)}$ is $(N, N^2) = (12, 144)$ and each small site on the figure has size $(1, N) = (1, 12)$. Generally a row has 2 $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ ’s with differing signs, whose *locations* are set by the ‘legs’ of $\partial/\partial v|_{ij} f$, namely $f_{i, j \pm 1}$. Note that for rows with

$j = 1$ or $j = N_v$ the velocity BC in (3.13b), deletes one of the ‘legs’ of the stencil. The vectors $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ then perform the integration itself, i.e. in row $n = (i - 1)N_v + j$ the $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ ’s are multiplied by \vec{u} ’s as in (5.19) and integrate over position steps $1, \dots, i$. A prefactor of $-e^2\Delta x/(8m\varepsilon_0)$ was pulled out of the matrix for readability.

	$f_{1,1}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{1,2}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{1,3}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{1,4}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{2,1}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{2,2}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{2,3}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{2,4}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{3,1}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{3,2}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{3,3}\vec{u}^T$	$f_{3,4}\vec{u}^T$
$f_{1,1}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$	0	0	0				0			
$f_{1,2}$	$-\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$	0								
$f_{1,3}$	0	$-\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$								
$f_{1,4}$	0	0	$-\mathbb{T}^{[1]}$	0								
$f_{2,1}$	0				0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[2]}$	0	0	0			
$f_{2,2}$					$-\mathbb{T}^{[2]}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[2]}$	0				
$f_{2,3}$					0	$-\mathbb{T}^{[2]}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[2]}$				
$f_{2,4}$					0	0	$-\mathbb{T}^{[2]}$	0				
$f_{3,1}$	0				0				0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[3]}$	0	0
$f_{3,2}$									$-\mathbb{T}^{[3]}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[3]}$	0
$f_{3,3}$									0	$-\mathbb{T}^{[3]}$	0	$+\mathbb{T}^{[3]}$
$f_{3,4}$									0	0	$-\mathbb{T}^{[3]}$	0

Figure 5.2: An example of the $F^{(2)}$ matrix, for a (3, 4) grid. On the left, the evolved vector \vec{u} is written out explicitly, its length is $N = 12$. The middle matrix is $F^{(2)}$ up to a constant factor of $-e^2\Delta x/(8m\varepsilon_0)$. The small cells are row vectors with length $N = 12$. The vector on top is $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ and it represents how the matrix multiplication mixes its elements. Gray elements are 0.

Generally, one may express $F^{(2)}$ as a block-diagonal sequence as

$$F^{(2)} = -\frac{e^2\Delta x}{8m\varepsilon_0} \cdot \bigoplus_{i=1}^{N_x} B_i = -\frac{e^2\Delta x}{8m\varepsilon_0} \cdot B_1 \oplus B_2 \oplus \dots \oplus B_{N_x}. \quad (5.20)$$

It may be seen on Fig. 5.2, our example, that it consists of $N_x = 3$ blocks, B_1, B_2, B_3 , which only differ in the superscript i on $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$. Generally, block B_i has size $(N_v, N_x N_v^2)$ and is given by

$$B_i = \begin{pmatrix} 0_{N_v-1, N_x N_v} & \mathbb{I}_{N_v-1} \otimes \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \\ 0_{1, N_x N_v} & 0_{1, (N_v-1) N_x N_v} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0_{1, (N_v-1) N_x N_v} & 0_{1, N_x N_v} \\ \mathbb{I}_{N_v-1} \otimes \mathbb{T}^{[i]} & 0_{N_v-1, N_x N_v} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.21)$$

The first matrix contains the ‘upper diagonal’ while the second one contains the ‘lower diagonal’, although remember that B_i is not square. The zero matrices have sizes such that both matrices in the above make sense mathematically and that the B_i ’s have correct sizes. The upper and lower ‘diagonals’ are built using Kronecker products with identity matrices. The zeros shift these up- or downwards.

An important thing to note here is that the electric field generation and the resulting force per mass are both species dependent generally via the charge q_s and charge-mass ratio q_s/m_s , respectively. In the one species case this is not relevant, therefore the prefactor in (5.20) could be separated from the blocks B_i . In Chapter 7 this idea is revisited and more general versions of (5.20-5.21) are given.

Chapter 6

Convergence and gate complexity for 1 species

This chapter builds on the results of the previous one to rigorously investigate the convergence of the quantum algorithm from Chapter 4, as well as its gate complexity in the asymptotic limit of $N_x, N_v \gg 1$, for 1 dynamical species. For this investigation, N_x, N_v and ν_0 (from (3.8)) are treated as the *control parameters* of the system, meaning that the scaling of each mathematical expression is realized with respect to them. On the other hand variables such as $x_{\max}, v_{\max}, \mathcal{N}, b$ are treated as fixed. Moreover, the coefficients ν_k for $k \geq 1$ from (3.8) are also treated as fixed and independent of the control parameters. This means $\mathcal{O}(\nu[v_{\max}]) = \mathcal{O}(\nu_0)$ and $\mathcal{O}(\nu[v_{\max}] - \nu_0) = \mathcal{O}(1)$. We shall show later that ν_0 has to increase as (N_x, N_v) increase to keep $R < 1$, therefore ν_0 is also treated as large within the calculations below. Finally, N_v is assumed to be even from now on. These assumptions simplify the computation of certain terms to some extent as it is shown later.

Remember that (3.11) fixes the relation between $N_x, \Delta x$ and x_{\max} as well as that (3.12) fixes the relation between $N_v, \Delta v$ and v_{\max} . This way Δx depends on N_x and similarly for Δv .

As a result of the characterization of the convergence of the quantum algorithm, a restrictive relationship between control parameters ν_0 and N_x, N_v is realized later on. That is used for the investigation of the gate complexity.

6.1 Proving convergence

6.1.1 Need for a bound

As discussed in Chapter 4, the quantum algorithm is only guaranteed to converge to the correct solution if $R < 1$ for

$$R = \frac{1}{|\mu(F^{(1)})|} \left(\|F^{(2)}\| \|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\| + \frac{\|F^{(0)}\|}{\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|} \right), \quad (6.1)$$

and also $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$. We are primarily interested in large grid-sizes, i.e. $N_x, N_v \gg 1$, to investigate a potential quantum advantage, however the numerical exact evaluation of R is very computationally expensive in that regime, due to the term $\|F^{(2)}\|$. Therefore, an upper bound for R needs to be calculated analytically in terms of the free parameters of the system, that can be evaluated instantly on a computer. Such a bound requires upper bounding the numerator and lower bounding the denominator. The bound will bring the additional benefit of providing a way to investigate the asymptotic behaviour of R as well as the gate complexity,

as the latter includes similar terms to those appearing in R . The bound has the form

$$R < R_{\text{bnd}} = \frac{1}{|\mu(F^{(1)})_{\text{bnd}}|} \left(\|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}} \|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\| + \frac{\|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}}{\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|} \right), \quad (6.2)$$

where ‘bnd’ stands for ‘bound’. \vec{u}_{in} needs to be chosen such that $\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ can be evaluated exactly. This is because it appears in both the numerator and the denominator in both R and the gate complexity. The next subsection goes over all the ‘ingredients’ that enter R_{bnd} . We also obtain their asymptotic scaling in the limit $N_x, N_v \gg 1$.

Note that the rescaling mentioned in Subsection 4.3.1 only concerns the evaluation of the gate complexity and not that of R , so it is not taken into account for now.

6.1.2 Ingredients for the bound

Obtaining $\mu(F^{(1)})_{\text{bnd}}$

Recall from Subsection 5.2.3 that $F^{(1)} = \hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)}$, where $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ is antisymmetric and $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ is diagonal. Then, using the definition of the log-norm, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(F^{(1)}) &= \lambda_{\max} \left(\frac{\hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)} + \left(\hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)}\right)^T}{2} \right) \\ &= \lambda_{\max}(\bar{F}^{(1)}) \\ &= \max_n [-\nu(v_{n//N_v})] \\ &= \max_j [-\nu(v_j)] \\ &= -\nu(v_{\lceil N_v/2 \rceil}) \\ &\leq -\nu_0, \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

where ν_0 is the minimum of the collision frequency function that was discussed in Section 3.2. Therefore $\mu(F^{(1)})_{\text{bnd}} = -\nu_0$ and hence $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$, as required. Note that a negative upper bound for $\mu(F^{(1)})$ means a lower bound on $|\mu(F^{(1)})|$ in the denominator of R . We see that without collisions, $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$ would not be satisfied in our model. See Appendix B for why it would never be satisfied for any ν_0 , if the E field was computed from Ampere’s law.

Obtaining $\|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}}$

The spectral norm $\|F^{(2)}\|$ cannot be evaluated using standard analytical methods, however it can upper bounded by the Frobenius norm $\|F^{(2)}\|_F$. Using the general definition of $F^{(2)}$ from (5.20-5.21), one can write

$$\left(\|F^{(2)}\|_F\right)^2 = \left(\frac{e^2 \Delta x}{8m\varepsilon_0}\right)^2 \sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \left(\|B_i\|_F\right)^2, \quad (6.4)$$

with

$$\left(\|B_i\|_F\right)^2 = 2(N_v - 1) \|\mathbb{T}^{[i]}\|^2. \quad (6.5)$$

The prefactor is due to $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ appearing in B_i exactly $2(N_v - 1)$ times. $\|\mathbb{T}^{[i]}\|^2$ can be computed from (5.18), its definition, as

$$\|\mathbb{T}^{[i]}\|^2 = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } i = 1 \\ \underbrace{(i-2)(N_v-2)4^2}_{\text{bulk terms}} + \underbrace{[2(N_v-2) + 2(i-2)]2^2}_{\text{edge terms}} + \underbrace{4 \cdot 1^2}_{\text{corner terms}} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (6.6)$$

Substituting (6.6) back into (6.5) and then (6.4), and after evaluating the sum over i , one finds

$$\left(\|F^{(2)}\|_F\right)^2 = \left(\frac{e^2\Delta x}{8m\varepsilon_0}\right)^2 \cdot 8(N_v - 1)(2N_v - 3)(N_x - 1)^2, \quad (6.7)$$

and hence the bound is

$$\|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}} = \|F^{(2)}\|_F = \frac{e^2\Delta x}{2\sqrt{2}m\varepsilon_0} \sqrt{(N_v - 1)(2N_v - 3)(N_x - 1)}. \quad (6.8)$$

It scales asymptotically as

$$\lim_{N_x, N_v \gg 1} \|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}} \longrightarrow \frac{e^2 x_{\text{max}}}{m\varepsilon_0} N_v = \mathcal{O}(N_v), \quad (6.9)$$

where the N_x dependence vanishes due to cancellation with Δx .

Obtaining $\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$

The initial condition is restricted by two factors. Firstly, as mentioned earlier, it needs to be exactly computable. Secondly, it has to be more *concentrated* in phase space than the Maxwellian (Gaussian) thermal state $f^M(v)$ encoded in $F^{(0)}$. This is fundamentally because the ratio $\|F^{(0)}\|/\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ must decrease as the system size (N_x, N_v) grows. Remember from (5.15) that the Gaussian in $F^{(0)}$ is weighted by the values of $\nu(v)$. This weighting can be thought of as being ‘cancelled’ by the ν_0 in $\mu(F^{(1)})$ in the denominator of R . With this cancellation the ratio $\|F^{(0)}\|/\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ becomes the norm of a Gaussian over the norm of \vec{u}_{in} . The more evenly distributed the elements of a vector are, the smaller its l_2 norm becomes. Consequently, \vec{u}_{in} must be more concentrated in phase space than $f^M(v)$.

The above two conditions are satisfied for a number of initial conditions. We choose a scenario in which 2 spatially uniform beams with opposite, definite velocities collide head-on. Then $f_{ij}(t=0) \propto \delta_{j,J} + \delta_{j,N_v-J+1}$, which encodes the 2 beams with velocities v_J and $-v_J$ for some J . The lack of i dependence ensures uniformity in x . This may be illustrated as

$$\vec{u}_{\text{in}} \propto \text{vec} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6.10)$$

where the 1’s are in the J ’s and $(N_v - J + 1)$ ’s columns. The proportionality constant can be fixed from requiring that $\iint f_{ij}(t=0) = \mathcal{N}$ on the full grid, using the trapezoidal rule for integration. After doing that, one gets

$$(u_{\text{in}})_n = \frac{\mathcal{N}}{\Delta x \Delta v N_x} (\delta_{n//N_v, J} + \delta_{n//N_v, N_v - J + 1}), \quad (6.11)$$

and

$$\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\| = \frac{\sqrt{2}\mathcal{N}}{\Delta x \Delta v \sqrt{N_x}}. \quad (6.12)$$

Asymptotically, it scales as

$$\lim_{N_x, N_v \gg 1} \|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\| \longrightarrow \frac{\mathcal{N} \sqrt{N_x N_v}}{2\sqrt{2} v_{\text{max}} x_{\text{max}}} = \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N_x N_v}). \quad (6.13)$$

Obtaining $\|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}$

Upper bounding $\|F^{(0)}\|$ is very nontrivial due to the Gaussian being weighted with varying collision frequencies. From (5.15), one can write its exact definition as

$$\|F^{(0)}\|^2 = \left(\frac{\mathcal{N}}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \right)^2 \left[\sum_{J=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-bv_J^2) \right]^{-2} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N \nu^2(v_{n//N_v}) \exp(-2bv_{n//N_v}^2), \quad (6.14)$$

where the n independent prefactors were pulled out of the sum. Now we may utilize the fact that within the sum the n dependence is purely $n // N_v = j$ dependence. Also, this implicit j dependence is symmetric around the middle, i.e. $\nu^2(v) \exp(-2bv^2) = \nu^2(-v) \exp(-2b[-v]^2)$, for even N_v which we assumed. Hence, (6.14) simplifies to

$$\|F^{(0)}\|^2 = \left(\frac{\mathcal{N}}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \right)^2 \left[\sum_{J=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-bv_J^2) \right]^{-2} \cdot 2N_x \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \nu^2(v_j) \exp(-2bv_j^2). \quad (6.15)$$

Bounding the second sum above can be done in different ways but since the bound on R is the most useful when it is a close one, it is crucial to identify the tightest possible bound. Before focusing on the different approaches, the sum over J in the prefactor is bounded from below, as that means bounding its reciprocal from above.

$$\sum_{J=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-bv_J^2) = -\exp(-bv_{\max}^2) + 2 \sum_{J=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-bv_J^2) \quad (6.16a)$$

$$\geq -\exp(-bv_{\max}^2) + 2 \int_{N_v/2+1}^{N_v+1} \exp(-bv_J^2) dJ \quad (6.16b)$$

$$= -\exp(-bv_{\max}^2) + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\Delta v \sqrt{b}} \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\Delta v \sqrt{b} \frac{N_v + 1}{2} \right) - \operatorname{erf} \left(\Delta v \sqrt{b} \frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (6.16c)$$

First, notice how the upper and lower limits are different in the two sums in (6.16a). Then the step from (6.16a) to (6.16b) is explained illustratively on Fig. 6.1. The collection of gray areas is equal to the sum and each increment of it between J and $J + 1$ for any $J \geq N_v/2 + 1$ is higher or equal to the integral between those points. This only works because v_J , as defined in (3.12) is a monotonically increasing function of J on $J \geq N_v/2 + 1$, hence $\exp(-bv_J^2)$ is monotonically decreasing. The step from (6.16b) to (6.16c) can be realized after making the substitution $z = \Delta v \sqrt{b} [J - (N_v + 1)/2]$ and then using the definition of the error function from Table 2.1. Hence, a closed form lower bound was obtained for the sum over J .

Upper bounding the sum over j in (6.15) was approached in 3 different ways. Below we outline the main steps in these approaches but detailed derivations are only given in Appendix C. The main difficulty originates from the fact that for non-constant (in this case monotonically increasing) $\nu(v)$, the values to be summed increase initially but then the exponential wins and they start decreasing. Therefore it is much more difficult to tackle than the J sum in the prefactor.

It is convenient to name the sum, therefore let

$$\mathcal{S} = \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \nu^2(v_j) \exp(-2bv_j^2). \quad (6.17)$$

Figure 6.1: Visual representation of how an integral can be used to lower bound a summation of monotonically non-increasing values, such as the exponential in (6.16a).

- **Method 1: Cauchy–Schwarz inequality**

Using the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality [35] one may write

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \sqrt{\left(\sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \nu^4(v_j) \right) \left(\sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-4bv_j^2) \right)}. \quad (6.18)$$

To bound the first sum above, each term in it must be upper bounded using the linear interpolation described in (3.9) that uses the minimum (ν_0) and the maximum ($\nu[v_{\max}]$) values of the collision frequency function. That results in a sum of values of a linear function to the 4th power, which may be upper bounded with an appropriate integral. The second sum above may be upper bounded by an integral similar to that in (6.16b–6.16c), remembering that this time the argument of the exponential has an additional factor of 4 as well as that we need an upper bound instead of a lower one. This procedure results in the bound

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S} &\leq \mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd 1}} = \\ &\sqrt{\frac{\left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v N_v - \nu(v_{\max}) + 2\nu_0 \right)^5 - \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v N_v - \nu(v_{\max}) + 2\nu_0 \right)^5}{5 \frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v}} \\ &\cdot \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4\Delta v \sqrt{b}} \left[\text{erf} \left(\Delta v \sqrt{b} (N_v - 1) \right) + \text{erf} \left(\Delta v \sqrt{b} \right) \right]}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.19)$$

The behaviour of the first square root above is well defined in the limit $\nu(v_{\max}) \rightarrow \nu_0^+$.

- **Method 2: factoring out $\nu(v_{\max})^2$**

Another approach is to use $\nu(v_j) \leq \nu(v_{\max})$, i.e.

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \nu(v_{\max})^2 \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-2bv_j^2). \quad (6.20)$$

Then, after bounding the Gaussian sum in a similar way as in method 1, one obtains the bound

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd } 2} = \nu(v_{\text{max}})^2 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{b}} \frac{1}{4\Delta v} \left[\text{erf} \left(\Delta v \sqrt{\frac{b}{2}} (N_v - 1) \right) + \text{erf} \left(\Delta v \sqrt{\frac{b}{2}} \right) \right]. \quad (6.21)$$

• **Method 3: partitioning the sum**

This method is the most sophisticated one of the 3. It is based on partitioning the sum in (6.17) into two segments such that within the first one the argument of the sum monotonically non-decreases and that within the second one the argument monotonically non-increases¹. Just as in method 1, the first step is to upper bound each $\nu(v_j)$ by the linear interpolation from (3.9). Next, the dummy variable is shifted, as $k = j - N_v/2$. Then, the terms to be summed are essentially realized as the values of a function that is a quadratic polynomial times an exponential of another quadratic polynomial. Treating k as continuous and denoting the mentioned function as $h(k)$, one may write $\mathcal{S} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{N_v/2} h(k)$, where

$$h(k) = \left[\frac{\nu(v_{\text{max}}) - \nu_0}{v_{\text{max}}} \Delta v \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \nu_0 \right]^2 \exp \left(-2b\Delta v^2 \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right). \quad (6.22)$$

The function $h(k)$ has a maximum at $k' > 0$, i.e. $h'(k') = 0$, where k' can be expressed analytically. We assume k' is not an integer, which can always be ensured by infinitesimally changing the system parameters. Hence, the first $\lceil k' \rceil - 1$ terms monotonically non-decrease and the last $N_v/2 - \lceil k' \rceil + 1$ terms monotonically non-increase. Different cases arise when k' is near 1 or $N_v/2$ but if it is in between, then the first $\lceil k' \rceil - 2$ and the last $N_v/2 - \lceil k' \rceil$ terms are bounded with integrals of $h(k)$ and the remaining 2 terms are added manually. This is illustrated on Fig. 6.2. The sum of the two grey areas plus the function values $h(\lceil k' \rceil - 1) + h(\lceil k' \rceil)$ make up the sum which is to be bounded. The mentioned antiderivative $H(k) = \int^k h(y)dy$ is

$$H(k) = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{16b^{3/2}\Delta v} \left[\left(\frac{\nu(v_{\text{max}}) - \nu_0}{v_{\text{max}}} \right)^2 + 4\nu_0^2 b \right] \text{erf} \left[\sqrt{2b}\Delta v(k - 1/2) \right] - \frac{\nu(v_{\text{max}}) - \nu_0}{4b\Delta v v_{\text{max}}} \left[\frac{\nu(v_{\text{max}}) - \nu_0}{v_{\text{max}}} \Delta v \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right) + 2\nu_0 \right] \exp \left[-2b\Delta v^2 \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (6.23)$$

Expressed in terms of $h(k)$ and $H(k)$, a closed form bound for \mathcal{S} is given by

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd } 3}^{(\text{case } 3)} = \underbrace{H(\lceil k' \rceil - 1) - H(1)}_{\geq \sum_{k=1}^{\lceil k' \rceil - 2} h(k)} + h(\lceil k' \rceil - 1) + h(\lceil k' \rceil) + \underbrace{H(N_v/2) - H(\lceil k' \rceil)}_{\geq \sum_{k=\lceil k' \rceil + 1}^{N_v/2} h(k)}, \quad (6.24)$$

which holds if $2 < \lceil k' \rceil < N_v/2$. That is case 3 in (C.12), the fully general expression. The above formula scales asymptotically as $H(N_v/2) - H(1)$.

It turns out that the asymptotic scaling of all 3 approaches are the same, assuming that $\mathcal{O}(\nu[v_{\text{max}}] - \nu_0) = \mathcal{O}(1)$ as it was discussed at the beginning of this chapter. That scaling is $\mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd } 1,2,3} = \mathcal{O}(N_v \nu_0^2)$. However, the numerical prefactors hidden by the big \mathcal{O} notation are quite different and they characterize how tight the bound is. Fig. 6.3 illustrates this difference and

Figure 6.2: Visual representation of the partitioning of the sum $\sum_{k=1}^{N_v/2} h(k)$ in method 3 for the case $2 < \lceil k' \rceil < N_v/2$. $h(k)$ peaks at some k' . The gray areas are bounded by appropriate integrals of $h(k)$. The blue dots represent the function values $h(\lceil k' \rceil - 1)$, $h(\lceil k' \rceil)$ separated from the integral bounds.

shows that method 3, using (C.12), is significantly tighter than the other two. Hence, it will be used to put our final tight bound on $\|F^{(0)}\|$.

Substituting (6.16c) and (C.12) into (6.15) we get $\|F^{(0)}\| \leq \|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}$ with

$$\|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}} = \frac{\mathcal{N}\sqrt{2N_x}}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \frac{\sqrt{\mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd } 3}}}{-\exp(-bv_{\max}^2) + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\Delta v \sqrt{b}} \left[\operatorname{erf}\left(\Delta v \sqrt{b} \frac{N_v + 1}{2}\right) - \operatorname{erf}\left(\Delta v \sqrt{b} \frac{1}{2}\right) \right]}, \quad (6.25)$$

which scales asymptotically as

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{N_x, N_v \gg 1} \|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}} &\rightarrow \frac{\mathcal{N}\sqrt{2N_x}\sqrt{b}}{2x_{\max}\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\sqrt{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right) - H(1)}}{\operatorname{erf}\left(\sqrt{b}v_{\max}\right)} \\ &\rightarrow \frac{\mathcal{N}}{4x_{\max}\sqrt{v_{\max}}} \left(\frac{2b}{\pi}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{\sqrt{\operatorname{erf}\left(\sqrt{2b}v_{\max}\right)}}{\operatorname{erf}\left(\sqrt{b}v_{\max}\right)} \sqrt{N_x N_v} \nu_0 \\ &= \mathcal{O}\left(\sqrt{N_x N_v} \nu_0\right), \end{aligned} \quad (6.26)$$

remembering that ν_0 is also large. Note in $H(N_v/2) - H(1)$, only the first term of $H(N_v/2)$ in (6.23) is kept, since the second one and $H(1)$ are smaller asymptotically.

¹We say ‘non-decrease’ instead of ‘increase’ in case $\nu(v)$ is constant, and similarly say ‘non-increase’ instead of ‘decrease’.

Figure 6.3: Comparison of the 3 methods for bounding \mathcal{S} on the range $N_v \in [10, 10000]$ (N_v even). Parameters: b , v_{\max} from Section 3.4 and $\nu(v) = 1 + (|v|/v_{\max})^2$. Note the logarithmic scaling of the vertical axis.

6.1.3 Bounding R

With all the ingredients computed, an upper bound for R is realized in the form of (6.2):

$$R_{\text{bnd}} = \frac{1}{|\mu(F^{(1)})_{\text{bnd}}|} \left(\|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}} \|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\| + \frac{\|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}}{\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|} \right), \quad (6.27)$$

where $\mu(F^{(1)})_{\text{bnd}}$, $\|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}}$, $\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ and $\|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}$ are given in (6.3,6.8,6.12,6.25), respectively.

Fig. 6.4 (a) shows how R and R_{bnd} vary with N_v for fixed N_x . The grid is small since the exact computation of $\|F^{(2)}\|$ takes a long time, this is partially the reason why the bound is useful. The collision frequency function is a toy model here with a second order dependence on v . That imposes a small variation on top of ν_0 , which was chosen such that $R, R_{\text{bnd}} \sim 1$. The bound gets better as N_v increases, due to the structure of $\|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}$. Fig. 6.4 (b) shows the behaviour of R_{bnd} for large square grids, as a function of ν_0 . For $N_v, N_x \gg 1$, the bounds increase as the grid grows, as expected. We chose the collision frequency here as well to be a quadratic function of v . Other physical constants are from the WIM setup, Section 3.4. We see that to simulate that system for a $\sim (10^3, 10^3)$ grid of physical relevance, the quantum algorithm requires $\nu_0 \sim 10^{18} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for guaranteed convergence. This is many orders of magnitude larger than the actual value in (3.24). For grids of this size, R_{bnd} is very tight, therefore we conclude that for $R \lesssim R_{\text{bnd}}$ to be < 1 , collisions have to be unphysically strong in our model.

(a) $R(N_v)$ vs $R_{bnd}(N_v)$ for varying N_v and fixed $N_x = 4$. Collision frequency: $\nu(v) = \nu_0 + 10^{12} \cdot (v/v_{\max})^2$ with $\nu_0 = 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

(b) $R_{bnd}(\nu_0)$ for different square grids, for varying ν_0 . Collision frequency: $\nu(v) = \nu_0 + 10^{15} \cdot (v/v_{\max})^2$.

Figure 6.4: Numerical testing of R_{bnd} . Values for constants are for WIM, from Section 3.4.

Using the asymptotic scalings derived previously, one finds the scaling of R_{bnd} to be

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{N_x, N_v \gg 1} R_{bnd} &= \frac{\mathcal{O}(N_v)\mathcal{O}(N_v\sqrt{N_x}) + \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N_x N_v}\nu_0)/\mathcal{O}(N_v\sqrt{N_x})}{\mathcal{O}(\nu_0)} \\
 &= \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{N_v^2\sqrt{N_x}}{\nu_0}\right) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_v}}\right) \\
 &= \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{N_v^2\sqrt{N_x}}{\nu_0}\right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.28}$$

The second term going to 0 is the result of our choice of \vec{u}_{in} . The $R_{\text{bnd}} \propto 1/\nu_0$ dependence can be observed on Fig. 6.4 (b) as well. Therefore we find, that in order to keep $\lim_{N_x, N_v \gg 1} R_{\text{bnd}} = \mathcal{O}(1)$ for varying (N_x, N_v) , ν_0 needs to increase as

$$\nu_0 \geq \mathcal{O}(N_v^2 \sqrt{N_x}). \quad (6.29)$$

This is the fundamental restriction imposed by the quantum algorithm on the dynamics of the system. For the case of a square grid, i.e. $N_x = N_v = \sqrt{N}$, we get

$$\nu_0 \geq \mathcal{O}(N^{5/4}) = \mathcal{O}\left(1/\varepsilon_d^{5/4}\right), \quad (6.30)$$

where $\varepsilon_d = \mathcal{O}(1/N)$ is the discretization error of the finite difference scheme.

6.2 Gate complexity

Below we upper bound the gate complexity, for square grids. We work in the region of convergence asymptotically, i.e we use (6.29). We first need to compute the scaling of the expressions that enter the gate complexity, as discussed in Subsection 4.4.

6.2.1 Ingredients for the gate complexity

Scaling of $\|F^{(1)}\|$

Another thing needed is the scaling of $\|F^{(1)}\|$, where $F^{(1)}$ was given in (5.16, 5.17a, 5.17b). We shall use the Frobenius norm again.

$$\begin{aligned} (\|F^{(1)}\|_F)^2 &= \underbrace{N_x \sum_{j=1}^{N_v} \nu^2(v_j)}_{(5.16)} + \underbrace{2N_x \sum_{j=1}^{N_v} \left(\frac{v_j}{2\Delta x}\right)^2}_{(5.17a)} \\ &\quad + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \sum_{j=1}^{N_v} \left(\frac{e^2 \mathcal{N}}{2m\varepsilon_0 \Delta v}\right)^2 \left(\frac{i-1}{N_x-1}\right)^2 (2 - \delta_{1,j} - \delta_{N_v,j})}_{(5.17b)} \quad (6.31) \\ &= \mathcal{O}(N_x N_v \nu_0^2) + \mathcal{O}(N_x^3 N_v) + \mathcal{O}(N_x N_v^3) \end{aligned}$$

The 3 scalings follow from the explicit evaluation of these sums. Now using (6.29) we get

$$(\|F^{(1)}\|_F)^2 \leq \mathcal{O}(N_x^2 N_v^5) + \mathcal{O}(N_x^3 N_v) + \mathcal{O}(N_x N_v^3), \quad (6.32)$$

hence

$$\|F^{(1)}\| \leq \mathcal{O}(N^{7/4}). \quad (6.33)$$

Scaling of $\|A\|$

Remember that (4.12) bounds $\|A\|$. To bound its scaling, we perform the rescaling discussed in Subsection 4.3.1 using (6.13), on (6.9, 6.26). We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|A\| &\leq N_c \left(\underbrace{\mathcal{O}(N)}_{\text{rescaled } \|F^{(0)}\|_{\text{bnd}}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(N^{7/4})}_{\text{unscaled } \|F^{(1)}\|_{\text{bnd}}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(N^{5/4})}_{\text{rescaled } \|F^{(2)}\|_{\text{bnd}}} \right) \quad (6.34) \\ &= N_c \mathcal{O}(N^{7/4}), \end{aligned}$$

where $\|F^{(1)}\|$ from (6.33) is unaffected by the rescaling and ends up being the largest.

Sparsity

The sparsity of $F^{(0)}$ is N since it is fully filled, that of $F^{(1)}$ is 5 and that of $F^{(2)}$ is $2N$ due to the 2 double integrals encoded per row. Hence,

$$s = \max \{ N, 5, 2N \} = 2N = \mathcal{O}(N). \quad (6.35)$$

Solution decay

The parameter g_u , as defined in (4.10), measures the decay of the norm of the solution and is unchanged by the rescaling so we ignore that here. To estimate this, we take $\vec{u}(T)$ to be a Maxwellian, which is a very good approximation for $T \gtrsim 1/\nu_0$. Remember that $F^{(0)}$ in (5.15) encodes a Maxwellian that is weighted by values of $\nu(v)$. Therefore, if we set $\nu_0 = 1$ in (6.26), the norm, we end up with $\|\vec{u}(T)\| = \mathcal{O}(N^{1/2})$. Then, substituting $\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ from (6.13) results in

$$g_u = \frac{\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|}{\|\vec{u}(T)\|} \approx \frac{\mathcal{O}(N^{3/4})}{\mathcal{O}(N^{1/2})} = \mathcal{O}(N^{1/4}). \quad (6.36)$$

Carleman steps

The number of Carleman linearization steps N_C , as defined in (4.11), scales logarithmically with N through $\|F^{(2)}\|$, $\|\vec{u}(T)\|$ and $\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$. Therefore, it can be ignored in our analysis as it is weaker than any polynomial dependency.

6.2.2 Asymptotic scaling of the gate complexity

We can finally obtain the scaling of gate complexity by substituting the above results into (4.9) as

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{O}\left(N^{1/4}TN^{7/4}\text{poly}(N)\right) \quad \cdot \quad \text{weak logarithmic dependencies} \\ & = \mathcal{O}\left(TN^2\text{poly}(N)\right) \quad \cdot \quad \text{weak logarithmic dependencies.} \end{aligned} \quad (6.37)$$

Note that $\text{poly}(\cdot)$ is some polynomial that can only be determined during the actual implementation of the quantum algorithm. For reference, the commonly used classical implementation of (3.20a-3.20d), the original system, has time complexity $\mathcal{O}(TN)$. Therefore the quantum one is polynomially larger, i.e. no quantum advantage is suggested by the above *upper* bound for the gate complexity.

Chapter 7

Mapping for S species

This chapter extends the results of Chapter 5 to an arbitrary number of dynamical species. We map the $(1 + 1)$ dimensional discretized Vlasov equation with S species, as formulated in (3.17a-3.17d), onto (4.1), the input of the quantum algorithm.

7.1 Vectorization of the distribution matrices

7.1.1 \vec{u}

Each species s has a distribution matrix $f^{(s)}$, therefore let us define $\vec{u}^{(s)} = \text{vec}(f^{(s)})$, just as in (5.1) for one species. Then the full state vector can be constructed by vertically stacking the individual state vectors of length $N_x N_v$ into a vector of length $S N_x N_v$ the following way

$$\vec{u} = \sum_{s=1}^S \vec{e}_s \otimes \vec{u}^{(s)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \vec{u}^{(1)} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \vec{u}^{(2)} + \dots + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \vec{u}^{(S)} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{u}^{(1)} \\ \vec{u}^{(2)} \\ \vdots \\ \vec{u}^{(S)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7.1)$$

where \vec{e}_s has a 1 in its s -th slot and 0's otherwise. The above vector has elements given by

$$u_n = f_{\lceil (n//N)/N_v \rceil, n//N_v}^{(\lceil n/N \rceil)}. \quad (7.2)$$

The species index can be computed as $s = \lceil n/N \rceil$ and tells which (N_x, N_v) grid n is at. The position index is $i = \lceil (n//N)/N_v \rceil$, where the $n//N$ returns the index within the grid of species s that n is at. The ceiling function returns the row index within that grid. The velocity index is $j = n//N_v$, as it was so far.

7.1.2 $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$

The vector $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ is then

$$\vec{u}^{\otimes 2} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{w}^{(1)} \\ \vec{w}^{(2)} \\ \vdots \\ \vec{w}^{(S)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7.3)$$

in which there are S segments $\{\vec{w}^{(s)}\}_{s=1, \dots, S}$ of the form

$$\vec{w}^{(s)} = \left[f_{1,1}^{(s)} \vec{u}^T \quad f_{1,2}^{(s)} \vec{u}^T \quad \dots \quad f_{N_x, N_v}^{(s)} \vec{u}^T \right]^T, \quad (7.4)$$

that contain \vec{u} exactly $N_x N_v$ times, weighted by each component of $\vec{u}^{(s)}$. Hence $\vec{u}^{\otimes 2}$ is $(SN_x N_v)^2$ dimensional and can be expanded as

$$\vec{u}^{\otimes 2} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{1,1}^{(1)} \vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ f_{N_x, N_v}^{(1)} \vec{u} \\ \hline f_{1,1}^{(2)} \vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ f_{N_x, N_v}^{(2)} \vec{u} \\ \hline \vdots \\ \hline f_{1,1}^{(S)} \vec{u} \\ \vdots \\ f_{N_x, N_v}^{(S)} \vec{u} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7.5)$$

7.2 Finding the matrices

The matrices are based on the versions for one species from Section 5.2.

7.2.1 $F^{(0)}$

The generalized $F^{(0)}$ matrix has elements

$$F_n^{(0)} = \frac{\mathcal{N}_{\lceil n/N \rceil}}{\Delta x \Delta v (N_x - 1)} \left[\sum_{J=1}^{N_v-1} \exp(-b_{\lceil n/N \rceil} v_J^2) \right]^{-1} \cdot \nu^{\lceil n/N \rceil} (v_{n//N_v}) \exp(-b_{\lceil n/N \rceil} v_{n//N_v}^2). \quad (7.6)$$

This corresponds to the vertical stacking of $F^{(0)}$ -like matrices for individual species, in the same way as how the multispecies \vec{u} was constructed. The only trick employed is $s = \lceil n/N \rceil$.

7.2.2 $F^{(1)}$

Again, the linear contribution is partitioned into two parts as $F^{(1)} = \hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)}$. Let $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ encode the collisional part of the linear evolution, (3.17c), and $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ encode the rest of the linear contributions, (3.17b). Hence, one obtains

$$\bar{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = -\nu^{\lceil n/N \rceil} (v_{n//N_v}) \delta_{k,n}, \quad (7.7)$$

where the $\delta_{k,n}$ encodes the proportionality with $f_{ij}^{(s)}$. For $\hat{F}^{(1)}$, the elements read

$$\hat{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = -\frac{v_{n//N_v}}{2\Delta x} \begin{cases} \delta_{k,n+N_v} - \delta_{k,n+N_v(N_x-1)} & \text{for } n // N \leq N_v \\ \delta_{k,n+N_v} - \delta_{k,n-N_v} & \text{for } N_v < n // N \leq N_v (N_x - 1) \\ \delta_{k,n-N_v(N_x-1)} - \delta_{k,n-N_v} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (7.8a)$$

$$-\frac{q_{\lceil n/N \rceil} q' \mathcal{N}'}{2m_{\lceil n/N \rceil} \varepsilon_0 \Delta v} \frac{\lceil (n // N) / N_v \rceil - 1}{N_x - 1} \begin{cases} \delta_{k,n+1} & \text{for } n // N_v = 1 \\ -\delta_{k,n-1} & \text{for } n // N_v = N_v \\ \delta_{k,n+1} - \delta_{k,n-1} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (7.8b)$$

The first term encodes $-v_j \partial/\partial x|_{ij} f^{(s)}$ and has 3 cases, which are equivalent to the 3 cases of (3.14). The second term encodes the expression $-(q_s q' / m_s \varepsilon_0) \partial/\partial v|_{ij} f^{(s)} \iint^{x_i} f'(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J$, in which the value of the integral was substituted from (3.19). The cases arise from the cases of (3.15). We used the new formulas $s = \lceil n/N \rceil$ and $i = \lceil (n \parallel N) / N_v \rceil$. Importantly, $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ is still antisymmetric, and $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ is still diagonal, just as in the one-species case.

Figure 7.1: An example of the $F^{(1)}$ matrix for $S = 3$ species, encoding the linear part of the evolution, for a $(4, 4)$ grid. On the left, the evolved vector \vec{u} is written out explicitly, its length is $3 \cdot 16 = 48$. The middle matrix is $F^{(1)} = \hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)}$. It contains 3 kinds of elements, denoted by 3 colours, whose origin is indicated on the bottom. Gray elements are 0. Some elements have value 0 because of the BCs. The vector on the top is also \vec{u} and it represents how the matrix multiplication mixes its elements.

The resulting matrix and its effect on the evolution is illustrated on Fig. 7.1 for $S = 3$ species on a $(4, 4)$ grid. Similarly to the one species case back on Fig. 5.1, the 3 colours represent the different contributions. The structure of the matrix is a block-diagonal chain, that could be represented as a direct sum of one-species $F^{(1)}$'s. The \vec{u} vector on top represents the matrix multiplication preformed, and as it can be seen, the individual $\vec{u}^{(s)}$'s are only evolved by the

linear combination of their own elements, i.e. there are no linear interspecies effects in our model (between *dynamical* species).

7.2.3 $F^{(2)}$

The building unit of the multispecies $F^{(2)}$ matrix is still the trapezoidal rule vector $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ from (5.18). Let us define the new object

$$C_i^{(S)} = [q_1 \quad q_2 \quad \dots \quad q_S] \otimes \mathbb{T}^{[i]} = [q_1 \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \quad q_2 \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \quad \dots \quad q_S \mathbb{T}^{[i]}]. \quad (7.9)$$

This is essentially $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ being repeated S times in a SN dimensional row vector, in which each $\mathbb{T}^{[i]}$ is weighted by the different charges. The point is that via matrix multiplication by \vec{u} , it computes the field $E(x_i)$ at x_i of the S species (not that of the background). Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} C_i^{(S)} \vec{u} &= [q_1 \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \quad q_2 \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \quad \dots \quad q_S \mathbb{T}^{[i]}] \begin{bmatrix} \vec{u}^{(1)} \\ \vec{u}^{(2)} \\ \vdots \\ \vec{u}^{(S)} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= q_1 \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \vec{u}^{(1)} + q_2 \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \vec{u}^{(2)} + \dots + q_S \mathbb{T}^{[i]} \vec{u}^{(S)} \\ &= \frac{4}{\Delta x \Delta v} \sum_{s=1}^S q_s \iint^{x_i} f^{(s)}(x_I, v_J) dx_I dv_J, \end{aligned} \quad (7.10)$$

which is proportional to the field at x_i as claimed, by a direct comparison to (3.17a) (where the dummy label is different). Therefore, the $C_i^{(S)}$'s control the field generation, and need to be placed and weighted in $F^{(2)}$ so that the right matrix multiplications are being enforced. First, we shall consider a concrete example for $S = 3$, for a (3, 3) grid, as indicated on Fig 7.2. A striking feature is that the evolution of $\vec{u}^{(s)}$ is governed by the elements of $\vec{w}^{(s)}$. The C_i 's are placed so that the elements of $\vec{w}^{(s)}$ picked out correspond to the 'legs' of the $\partial/\partial v|_{ij}$ operator, just as in the one-species case. The content of C_i performs the integration discussed above. Each \vec{u} needed in (7.10) comes from elements of $\vec{w}^{(s)}$, that elements are specified by the location of the C_i 's. Note that due to the small grid, 2 out of 3 rows are edge cases with only 1 'leg'.

To represent this generally, we upgrade the blocks from (5.21) to

$$B_i^{(S)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0_{N_v-1, SN_x N_v} & \mathbb{I}_{N_v-1} \otimes C_i^{(S)} \\ 0_{1, SN_x N_v} & 0_{1, (N_v-1) SN_x N_v} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0_{1, (N_v-1) SN_x N_v} & 0_{1, SN_x N_v} \\ \mathbb{I}_{N_v-1} \otimes C_i^{(S)} & 0_{N_v-1, SN_x N_v} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (7.11)$$

where the sizes of the zeros have been adjusted. The first matrix contains the 'upper diagonal' while the second one contains the 'lower diagonal', which can be seen in our example too, where each species has 3 blocks with each block containing both $+C_i$ and $-C_i$, $N_v - 1 = 2$ times. Note that a superscript (S) is written on $C_i^{(S)}$ in the equation but not on Fig. 7.2 for clarity. Then, one may express $F^{(2)}$ extremely compactly as

$$F^{(2)} = -\frac{\Delta x}{8\epsilon_0} \cdot \bigoplus_{s=1}^S \left(\frac{q_s}{m_s} \bigoplus_{i=1}^{N_x} B_i^{(S)} \right), \quad (7.12)$$

which is essentially two direct summations embedded into each other. The s -th term in the first direct sum evolves species s . The term responsible for that,

$$\frac{q_s}{m_s} \bigoplus_{i=1}^{N_x} B_i^{(S)}, \quad (7.13)$$

has exactly the same form as (5.20) for one species, but here it is weighted by the factor q_s/m_s , which determines the local acceleration of species s caused by the field. The same factor appears in the encoded scheme, (3.17a), and is indicated on Fig. 7.2 on the left. If we set $S = 1$, then q_1 can be factored from $C_i^{(S=1)}$ and hence from $B_i^{(S=1)}$. Combining that with the single q_1/m_1 factor in (7.12) and setting $q_1 = -e$, $m_1 = m$, one recovers (5.20). Also note that $B_i^{(S)}$ is the same for all species, hence the S label instead of s . This is because the same field accelerates all species, the differences arise in the values of the acceleration caused. Written out for Fig. 7.2, our example, (7.12) reads

$$F_{\text{example}}^{(2)} = -\frac{\Delta x}{8\varepsilon_0} \cdot \left[\frac{q_1}{m_1} \left(B_1^{(S=3)} \oplus B_2^{(S=3)} \oplus B_3^{(S=3)} \right) \right] \oplus \left[\frac{q_2}{m_2} \left(B_1^{(S=3)} \oplus B_2^{(S=3)} \oplus B_3^{(S=3)} \right) \right] \oplus \left[\frac{q_3}{m_3} \left(B_1^{(S=3)} \oplus B_2^{(S=3)} \oplus B_3^{(S=3)} \right) \right]. \quad (7.14)$$

An explicit map for the elements of $F^{(2)}$, like the one for one species in Appendix A, can be derived from the above formulas but that is left to future work.

7.3 Remarks on convergence and gate complexity

Investigating the convergence of the quantum algorithm and its gate complexity for S species is possible by generalizing the results of Chapter 6. However, we shall not cover it in its entirety here but only give a couple of remarks about important points.

The structures of the matrices $F^{(0)}$, $F^{(1)}$ and $F^{(2)}$ are very similar to those of the $S = 1$ versions. Therefore, we expect the scaling of $\|F^{(0)}\|$, $\|F^{(1)}\|$, and $\|F^{(2)}\|$ to behave the same way asymptotically as for $S = 1$. Note that scaling with respect to S can be ignored since S is a low integer for all the physical scenarios of interest. As for $\mu(F^{(1)})$, knowing that $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ is still antisymmetric and $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ is still diagonal, we can bound it as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(F^{(1)}) &= \lambda_{\max} \left(\frac{\hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)} + \left(\hat{F}^{(1)} + \bar{F}^{(1)} \right)^T}{2} \right) \\ &= \lambda_{\max} \left(\bar{F}^{(1)} \right) \\ &= \max_{n,s} \left\{ -\nu^{(s)}(v_{n//N_v}) \right\} \\ &= \max_{j,s} \left\{ -\nu^{(s)}(v_j) \right\} \\ &= -\min_s \left\{ \nu^{(s)}(v_{\lceil N_v/2 \rceil}) \right\} \\ &\leq -\min_s \nu_0^{(s)}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.15)$$

Therefore $\mu(F^{(1)})_{\text{bnd}} = -\min_s \nu_0^{(s)}$ and $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$ is still satisfied. The above means that the *least* collisional species specifies the log-norm. Next, one has to choose a \vec{u}_{in} such that it is more concentrated in phase space than $F^{(0)}$ to keep $\|F^{(0)}\|/\|\vec{u}_{\text{in}}\|$ low. Then, putting these together and using the exact same bounding machinery as in Subsection 6.1.2, an R_{bnd} may be realized. Also, a relationship similar to (6.29) can be established between the collision frequencies and the grid size. That can be used later to obtain the scaling of the gate complexity. We expect that to be the same with respect to N as in the $S = 1$ case.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} \vec{u}^{(1)} \\ \vec{u}^{(2)} \\ \vec{u}^{(3)} \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} \vec{w}^{(1)T} \\ \vec{w}^{(2)T} \\ \vec{w}^{(3)T} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \vec{w}^{(1)T} & \vec{w}^{(2)T} & \vec{w}^{(3)T} \end{pmatrix}$$

$\frac{q_1}{m_1}$	$\frac{q_2}{m_2}$	$\frac{q_3}{m_3}$	$\vec{w}^{(1)T}$	$\vec{w}^{(2)T}$	$\vec{w}^{(3)T}$
0	0	0	0	0	0
$+C_1$	$+C_2$	$+C_3$	$+C_1$	$+C_2$	$+C_3$
$-C_1$	$-C_2$	$-C_3$	$-C_1$	$-C_2$	$-C_3$
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0			

Chapter 8

Summary and prospects

In this report we showed for the first time how the nonlinear Vlasov equation can be solved on a future quantum computer, using the quantum algorithm in [26]. In Chapter 5 we derived a mapping from the discretized Vlasov equation onto (4.1), the input of [26], and generalized that to S species in Chapter 7. For one species, we showed in Chapter 6 that the convergence parameter R can be efficiently upper bounded with R_{bnd} which can be evaluated instantly even for large grid sizes. This way one can set the collision frequency such that $R \leq R_{\text{bnd}} < 1$ is satisfied. However, for interstellar plasma, our test scenario, we found that convergence requires the collision frequency to be unphysically large. We also found that the upper bound for the gate complexity is polynomially larger than the classical time complexity with respect to grid size.

It is however important to note that the mentioned bound for the gate complexity was derived in [26] without assuming structured patterns in its input matrices. Since the matrices in our case have repeating segments, it is highly likely that the actual gate complexity is lower than the upper bound. Furthermore, the development of quantum algorithms with the same input formalism as (4.1) is a very active area of research, partially because higher dimensional polynomial nonlinearities can be transformed into quadratic ones [36]. Hence it is likely that quantum algorithms with less strict constraints and lower complexities will be put forward, and then our mapping will be applicable to those without major modifications required.

Future work could be directed at implementing more complex collision operators with the hope of pushing the regime of convergence closer to physically meaningful scenarios. Constructing the mapping for the full (3 + 3) dimensional model is also to be done. That will probably have to be in the non-relativistic limit, as that makes (3.2-3.3) a system of differential- and not that of *delay* differential equations. That is required since (4.1) is an example of the former. Another approach could be performing an integral transform of some kind on the plasma model that results in the elimination of the integrals in Maxwell's equations. That would reduce the sparsity of the input matrices and potentially the gate complexity.

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Appendix A

Expression for the elements of $F^{(2)}$

On the next page, the elements of $F^{(2)}$ are written out, for 1 species. The map below is equivalent to (5.20-5.21). The cases are explained as follows. Remember that the state vector index n and the grid indices (i, j) are related by $\lceil n/N_v \rceil = i$, $n \parallel N_v = j$ and $n = (i-1)N_v + j$.

1. Case $\{n < N_v + 1\}$ evolves f_{ij} with $i = 1$, when the integral of the ion background is 0 by definition.
2. Case $\{\lceil n/N_v \rceil \geq 2$ and $n \parallel N_v = 1\}$ evolves f_{ij} with $i \geq 2$ and $j = 1$, where the left ‘leg’ of $\partial/\partial v|_{ij}f$ vanishes due to BCs.
3. Case $\{\lceil n/N_v \rceil \geq 2$ and $n \parallel N_v = N_v\}$ evolves f_{ij} with $i \geq 2$ and $j = N_v$, where the right ‘leg’ of $\partial/\partial v|_{ij}f$ vanishes due to BCs.
4. The last case is the general one, in which both ‘legs’ exist.

Double sums are responsible for integrating over bulk elements of the grid, single sums for integrating over edge elements and single deltas for integrating over corner elements. For $\lceil n/N_v \rceil = 2$ the double sums vanish.

$$F_{n,k}^{(2)} = -\frac{e^2 \Delta x}{8m\varepsilon_0}.$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
& \left\{ \begin{aligned}
& 0 \\
& +2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + (I-1)N_v + 1} + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + IN_v} \\
& +2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + J} + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + J} \\
& +4 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + (I-1)N_v + J}
\end{aligned} \right. & \text{for } n < N_v + 1 \\
& - \left\{ \begin{aligned}
& \delta_{k, N(n-2)+1} + \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + 1} + \delta_{k, N(n-2) + N_v} \\
& + \delta_{k, N(n-2) + \lfloor n/N_v \rfloor N_v} + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (I-1)N_v + 1} \\
& + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + IN_v} + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + J} \\
& + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + J} + 4 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (I-1)N_v + J}
\end{aligned} \right. & \text{for } \left\lfloor \frac{n}{N_v} \right\rfloor \geq 2 \\
& & \text{and } n \not\parallel N_v = 1 \\
& \left. \left[\begin{aligned}
& \delta_{k, Nn+1} + \delta_{k, Nn + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + 1} + \delta_{k, Nn + N_v} + \delta_{k, Nn + \lfloor n/N_v \rfloor N_v} \\
& + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + (I-1)N_v + 1} + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + IN_v} \\
& + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + J} + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + J} \\
& + 4 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, Nn + (I-1)N_v + J} \right] - \left[\delta_{k, N(n-2)+1} \right. \\
& + \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + 1} + \delta_{k, N(n-2) + N_v} + \delta_{k, N(n-2) + \lfloor n/N_v \rfloor N_v} \\
& + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (I-1)N_v + 1} + 2 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + IN_v} \\
& + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + J} + 2 \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1)N_v + J} \\
& \left. + 4 \sum_{I=2}^{\lfloor n/N_v \rfloor - 1} \sum_{J=2}^{N_v - 1} \delta_{k, N(n-2) + (I-1)N_v + J} \right] & \text{else}
\end{aligned} \right.
\end{aligned}
\right. \tag{A.1}$$

Appendix B

Coupling to Ampere's law

Below we discuss the effect of coupling to Ampere's law instead of Gauss's in the one species model. In that case, using the right side of (3.5), (3.6) would become

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} &= -v \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} + \frac{e}{m} E \frac{\partial f}{\partial v} + C[f] \\ \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} &= \frac{e}{\varepsilon_0} \int v f dv,\end{aligned}\tag{B.1}$$

where we dropped the (e) label and assumed that the ion background f' is a Maxwellian, i.e. $\int f' v dv = 0$. Therefore E is evolved in time just as f . The background only affects the initialization of the E field but not the evolution. Then, let $f_{i,j}$ approximate $f(x_i, v_j)$ and E_i approximate $E(x_i)$. By approximating the integral with the trapezoidal rule, one obtains the finite difference equations

$$\frac{d}{dt} f_{ij} = + \frac{e}{m} E_i \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \right|_{ij} f \quad \mathcal{O}(E^1 f^1) \tag{B.2a}$$

$$- v_j \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right|_{ij} f \quad \mathcal{O}(f^1) \tag{B.2b}$$

$$- \nu(v_j) f_{ij} \quad \mathcal{O}(f^1) \tag{B.2c}$$

$$+ \nu(v_j) f_j^M \quad \mathcal{O}(f^0) \tag{B.2d}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} E_i = \frac{e \Delta v}{\varepsilon_0} \left[\frac{v_1 f_{i,1} + v_{N_v} f_{i,N_v}}{2} + \sum_{J=2}^{N_v-1} v_J f_{iJ} \right], \quad \mathcal{O}(f^1) \tag{B.2e}$$

where f_j^M is from (3.21) and discrete differential operators are the same as before. Then, (B.2a) would be encoded in $F^{(2)}$, (B.2b,B.2e) in $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ (B.2c) in $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ and (B.2d) in $F^{(0)}$.

The state vector has length $N_x N_v + N_x = N_x(N_v + 1)$ and becomes

$$\vec{u} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{1,1} \\ \vdots \\ f_{1,N_v} \\ f_{2,1} \\ \vdots \\ f_{2,N_v} \\ \vdots \\ f_{N_x,N_v} \\ \hline E_1 \\ \vdots \\ E_{N_x} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

with elements

$$u_n = \begin{cases} f_{[n/N_v], n//N_v} & \text{for } 1 \leq n \leq N_x N_v \\ E_{n-N_x N_v}, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The fundamental problem with coupling to Ampere's law is that $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$ is not satisfied. To see this, we need the maps

$$\hat{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = \begin{cases} -\frac{v_{n//N_v}}{2\Delta x} \cdot \begin{cases} \delta_{k,n+N_v} - \delta_{k,n+N_v(N_x-1)} & \text{for } n \leq N_v \\ \delta_{k,n+N_v} - \delta_{k,n-N_v} & \text{for } N_v < n \leq N_v(N_x-1) \\ \delta_{k,n-N_v(N_x-1)} - \delta_{k,n-N_v} & \text{for } N_v(N_x-1) < n \leq N_v N_x \end{cases} \\ \frac{\Delta v e}{\varepsilon_0} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N_v} \delta_{k,(n-N_x N_v-1)N_v+j} v_j + \frac{v_{\max}}{2} (\delta_{k,(n-N_x N_v-1)N_v+1} - \delta_{k,(n-N_x N_v)N_v}) \right] & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

and

$$\bar{F}_{n,k}^{(1)} = \begin{cases} -\nu(v_{n//N_v})\delta_{k,n} & \text{for } n \leq N_v N_x \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

An example of this is given in Fig. B.1 for a (4, 4) grid. Notice that the first $N = 16$ rows and columns look like Fig. 5.1, except that the green terms encoding the integral of the ion background do not exist here. Also, $\bar{F}^{(1)}$ is still diagonal but the last N_x elements of the diagonal are 0. Furthermore, $\hat{F}^{(1)}$ is not antisymmetric due the bottom part that encodes (B.2e). The last $N_x = 4$ columns are empty because E only takes part in the nonlinear evolution, (B.2a), and not the linear one, regardless of the discretization scheme used.

As a result of the N_x empty columns, we know there are at least N_x eigenvalues of $F^{(1)}$ that are 0. Their eigenvectors have the form $[0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0]$ with the 1 being in one of the last N_x slots. Therefore $\alpha(F^{(1)}) \geq 0$ with $\alpha(F^{(1)})$ being the largest of the real parts of eigenvalues of $F^{(1)}$. We now use (2.5) to find

$$0 \leq \alpha(F^{(1)}) \leq \mu(F^{(1)}). \quad (\text{B.7})$$

The quantum algorithm would not converge because $\mu(F^{(1)}) < 0$ is not satisfied, regardless of the parameters in (B.2a-B.2e). This is unaffected by our choice of ordering the f_{ij} 's and E_i 's within \vec{u} , there will always be empty columns and 0 eigenvalues.

Figure B.1: An example of the $F^{(1)}$ matrix for a $(4, 4)$ grid with Ampere's law. On the left, \vec{u} is written out explicitly. The middle matrix is $F^{(1)}$. It contains 3 kinds of elements, denoted by 3 colours, as indicated on the right. Gray elements are 0. The vector on the top is also \vec{u} and it represents how the matrix multiplication mixes its elements.

Appendix C

Derivation of bounds for $\left\|F^{(0)}\right\|$

Below we derive the 3 methods for bounding \mathcal{S} from Subsection 6.1.2. That is needed to bound $\left\|F^{(0)}\right\|$. Remember,

$$\mathcal{S} = \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \nu^2(v_j) \exp(-2bv_j^2). \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Method 1

In method 1, we applied the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality [35] to \mathcal{S} and got

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \sqrt{\left(\sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \nu^4(v_j)\right) \left(\sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-4bv_j^2)\right)}. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

The argument of the first sum may be bounded using (3.9) as

$$\begin{aligned} \nu^4(v_j) &\leq \left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} v_j + \nu_0\right)^4 \\ &= \left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v(j-1) + 2\nu_0 - \nu(v_{\max})\right)^4. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Hence we bound the first sum as

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \nu^4(v_j) \\ &\leq \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v(j-1) + 2\nu_0 - \nu(v_{\max})\right)^4 \\ &\leq \int_{N_v/2+1}^{N_v+1} \left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v(j-1) + 2\nu_0 - \nu(v_{\max})\right)^4 dj \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v N_v - \nu(v_{\max}) + 2\nu_0\right)^5 - \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v N_v - \nu(v_{\max}) + 2\nu_0\right)^5}{5 \frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

The above expression goes to $N_v \nu_0^4$ in the limit $\nu(v_{\max}) \rightarrow \nu_0^+$. The second sum in (C.2) can be bounded as

$$\sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-4bv_j^2) \leq \int_{N_v/2}^{N_v} \exp(-4bv_j^2) dj. \quad (\text{C.5})$$

Now substituting $z = 2\sqrt{b}\Delta v(j - [N_v + 1]/2)$ results in

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-4bv_j^2) &\leq \int_{-\sqrt{b}\Delta v}^{\sqrt{b}\Delta v(N_v-1)} \exp(-z^2) dz \\ &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{b}\Delta v} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \left[\operatorname{erf}\left(\Delta v\sqrt{b}(N_v-1)\right) + \operatorname{erf}\left(\Delta v\sqrt{b}\right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

Finally, substituting (C.4) and (C.6) into (C.2), we obtain (6.19) as claimed.

Method 2

Method 2 uses $\nu(v_j) \leq \nu(v_{\max})$ and factors out $\nu(v_{\max})$ as

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \nu(v_{\max})^2 \sum_{j=N_v/2+1}^{N_v} \exp(-2bv_j^2). \quad (\text{C.7})$$

The sum can be bounded the same way as in (C.6) with the substitution $b \rightarrow b/2$. That gives the result claimed in (6.21).

Method 3

In method 3, by shifting the variable in (C.1) to $k = j - N_v/2$ and using the same interpolation to bound $\nu(v_j)$ as in (C.3), one obtains

$$\mathcal{S} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{N_v/2} h(k), \quad (\text{C.8})$$

with

$$h(k) = \left[\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \nu_0 \right]^2 \exp \left(-2b\Delta v^2 \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right). \quad (\text{C.9})$$

By solving $dh/dk|_{k=k'} = 0$, one gets

$$k' = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\nu_0}{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0} \frac{v_{\max}}{\Delta v} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{2b\Delta v^2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\nu_0}{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0} \frac{v_{\max}}{\Delta v} \right)^2} \quad (\text{C.10})$$

for the positive root, i.e. $k' > 0$. Therefore $h(k)$ is maximal at $k = k'$. The antiderivative $H(k) = \int^k h(y) dy$ of $h(k)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} H(k) &= \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{16b^{3/2}\Delta v} \left[\left(\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \right)^2 + 4\nu_0^2 b \right] \operatorname{erf} \left[\sqrt{2b}\Delta v(k - 1/2) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{4b\Delta v v_{\max}} \left[\frac{\nu(v_{\max}) - \nu_0}{v_{\max}} \Delta v \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right) + 2\nu_0 \right] \exp \left[-2b\Delta v^2 \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.11})$$

ignoring the integration constant. Finally, different cases have to be introduced to bound \mathcal{S} based on the value of $\lceil k' \rceil$. That, by symmetry, cannot be lower than 1. These cases can be summarized as

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd 3}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll}
\underbrace{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right) - H(1) + h(1)}_{\geq \sum_{k=2}^{N_v/2} h(k)} & \text{for } \lceil k' \rceil = 1 \\
\underbrace{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right) - H(2) + h(1) + h(2)}_{\geq \sum_{k=3}^{N_v/2} h(k)} & \text{for } \lceil k' \rceil = 2 \\
\underbrace{H(\lceil k' \rceil - 1) - H(1) + h(\lceil k' \rceil - 1) + h(\lceil k' \rceil)}_{\geq \sum_{k=1}^{\lceil k' \rceil - 2} h(k)} + \underbrace{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right) - H(\lceil k' \rceil)}_{\geq \sum_{k=\lceil k' \rceil + 1}^{N_v/2} h(k)} & \text{for } 2 < \lceil k' \rceil < \frac{N_v}{2} \\
\underbrace{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2} - 1\right) - H(1) + h\left(\frac{N_v}{2} - 1\right) + h\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right)}_{\geq \sum_{k=1}^{N_v/2 - 2} h(k)} & \text{for } \lceil k' \rceil = \frac{N_v}{2} \\
\underbrace{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right) - H(1) + h\left(\frac{N_v}{2}\right)}_{\geq \sum_{k=1}^{N_v/2 - 1} h(k)} & \text{for } \lceil k' \rceil = \frac{N_v}{2} + 1 \\
\underbrace{H\left(\frac{N_v}{2} + 1\right) - H(1)}_{\geq \sum_{k=1}^{N_v/2} h(k)} & \text{for } \lceil k' \rceil > \frac{N_v}{2} + 1,
\end{array} \right. \quad (\text{C.12})$$

with $\mathcal{S} \leq \mathcal{S}_{\text{bnd 3}}$. These cases may be realized visually, just as the general case (case 3 here) was explained with Fig. 6.2. All have the same asymptotic scaling.